

D8.3: Short- & medium-term FLW policy recommendations

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Contents

Document information	4
Glossary of terms and acronyms used.....	7
Executive summary.....	8
1. Introduction.....	9
1.1 ZeroW project summary.....	9
1.2 Mapping ZeroW outputs.....	12
1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	14
2. The WP8 approach: grounded policy recommendations.....	15
2.1 Building on the methodology and insights of T8.2.....	15
2.2 The conceptual rationale and policy context of the EU Policy Briefs.....	17
3. The five ZeroW EU Policy Briefs	22
POLICY BRIEF: BUILDING CONSUMER CAPACITY FOR A JUST ZERO FOOD WASTE TRANSITION	22
POLICY BRIEF: EMPOWERING FARMERS FOR A JUST ZERO FOOD WASTE TRANSITION	28
POLICY BRIEF: TRANSFORMING FOOD CHAIN STRUCTURE TO REDUCE FOOD LOSS AND WASTE (FLW).....	37
POLICY BRIEF: PARTICIPATORY LOCAL GOVERNANCE AND EMPOWERMENT FOR JUST ZERO FOOD WASTE TRANSITION WITHIN THE URBAN CONTEXT	45
POLICY BRIEF: EFFECTIVE GOVERNANCE FOR A JUST ZERO FOOD WASTE TRANSITION	52
4. Intended use and dissemination of the ZeroW EU Policy Briefs	57
5. Conclusions	59
References	61

List of figures

Figure 1: ZeroW at a glance	9
Figure 2: ZeroW approach	10
Figure 3: WP8 tasks, deliverables, objectives.....	10
Figure 4: Overview of the Just Pathway Actions (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2).....	17
Figure 5: Overview of the key policy recommendations.....	60

List of tables

Table 1: Glossary of terms and acronyms used	7
Table 2: Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description	13
Table 3: Final proposal for just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets (2030) (ZeroW Deliverable D8.2, 2025).....	16

Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
AFNs	Alternative Food Networks
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CSA	Community Supported Agriculture
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
FSC	Food Supply Chain
F2F	Farm to Fork
GHG	Greenhouse gas
NGOs	Non-governmental Organisations
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SFSCs	Short Food Supply Chains
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Lab
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
WP	Work Package

Table 1: Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Executive summary

This report, the third and final deliverable from the ZeroW Policy Team (WP8), translates the 'just pathway' framework and its associated actions into practical policy recommendations. Building on the FLW reduction targets outlined in D8.2, it provides short- and medium-term strategies for policymakers.

The goal is to present these recommendations as accessible EU Policy Briefs for effective dissemination. The briefs focus on **four priority areas**: 1) actor specific policies for consumers and farmers; 2) food chain structure with emphasis on short food supply chains; 3) governance that integrates FLW reduction into frameworks and strategies; and 4) context specific measures centred on the urban environment. This selection reflects their central role in systemic change and is informed by ZeroW economic modelling, stakeholder engagement and Living Lab activities.

The report outlines the rationale and policy context for the briefs, with specific reference to the completion of the Waste Framework Directive revision, and reflects on remaining gaps, ongoing debates, and advocacy windows. It then presents the extended versions of the **five EU Policy Briefs as published online**, which explore each topic in depth and provide clear cross references to T8.2. The briefs identify the following immediate priorities for policy and practice.

Consumer policy must treat behaviour as a core element of policy design. Priorities include food waste educational modules embedded in school curricula and community-level engagement that empowers rather than stigmatises people, such as peer-driven challenges, with a focus on redesigning choice environments rather than relying on negative messaging. **For farmers**, targeted infrastructural support is essential to narrow a widening digital divide. Public funds should pair connectivity with climate smart practices and high-quality advisory services, while procurement must account for capability and willingness to avoid underperformance and loss of trust. As structural barriers persist, **short food supply chains** offer potential but require appropriate logistics, food safety capacity, and fair access to public procurement. **At urban level**, multi-level governance is needed. National frameworks should set targets and reporting rules, while municipalities coordinate prevention across schools, hospitals, markets, and charities, with local funding tied to smart sustainable procurement and supported by comparable indicators. Finally, **overarching food governance** still lacks a coherent toolkit. With the Waste Framework Directive revision as an anchor, incentives should be aligned with measured reductions through outcome-based grants for municipalities, preferential finance for retailers that meet milestones, and mandatory reporting, while guarding against unintended negative consequences.

Together, these briefs serve as a **resource for EU and national policymakers, aiding agenda-setting and prioritisation**. They support a **just transition** toward near-zero FLW by 2050. The report concludes with guidance on immediate implementation and dissemination strategies to maximise policy impact.

1. Introduction

This chapter provides a high-level overview of the ZeroW project and more specifically Work Package 8 (WP8) (Section 1.1). Section 1.2 maps the ZeroW outputs within T8.3 of WP8. Subsequently, the chapter provides a detailed overview of the deliverable and its structure (Section 1.3)

1.1 ZeroW project summary

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (0FLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

Figure 1: ZeroW at a glance

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements:

Figure 2: ZeroW approach

To reach its goals ZeroW is divided into 11 WPs with different goals, tasks and deliverables. Figure 3 shows an overview of the WP8 composition.

Figure 3: WP8 tasks, deliverables, objectives

This report showcases the entire process of T8.3 and the related work that was carried out to reach short- and medium-term FLW policy recommendations. It builds on the comprehensive analysis in T8.2, starting with the conceptualisation of a “just pathway” and assessing the feasible intermediate FLW-reduction targets identified. The resulting policy recommendations are presented in five context-specific policy briefs, each informed by the “Just Pathway Actions” defined at the end of T8.2. Collectively, the briefs consolidate these insights and examples into a coherent policymaking framework.

1.2 Mapping ZeroW outputs

This report is the third and final deliverable of *WP8 - Policy recommendations for just transition to near-zero FLW*. WP8 focuses on providing alternative transition pathways towards near-zero FLW in 2050, indicating a 'just' transition pathway and intermediate targets to get to this situation, and finally providing short-, medium-term policy recommendations for policymakers across the EU.

The purpose of this chapter is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D8.3 Short- & medium-term FLW policy recommendations	<i>Will report on the process of defining actor-, chain, gender- governance-specific recommendations.</i>	<i>All chapters and sections.</i>	<i>This document provides a comprehensive report on the process, activities, and results of defining context-specific short- and medium-term FLW policy recommendations.</i>
TASKS			
T8.3 Short- & medium-term FLW policy recommendations	Specific policy recommendations will be provided, focusing at the short- and medium-term to facilitate the realisation of the 'just' transition pathway to 2050. These will use T8.2 as a starting point, but will also be aligned on ongoing debates and advocacy opportunities for change and development of EU and local policies. These will be delivered in the form of EU Policy Briefs, including for example: (i) food actor	<i>Chapters 3 and 4.</i>	This document provides a report of the following activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Revisiting the WP8 approach, the methodology, and insights from T8.2 to showcase the conceptual rationale and policy context of the EU Policy Briefs (Chapter 2).

	<p>specific briefs, focusing on the farm, food processing, retail, consumer and alternative valorisation stages; (ii) food chain structure specific brief, focusing on short food supply chains; (iii) context-specific brief, focusing on the required policies at the urban environment, where most of the food waste occurs; (iv) governance-specific brief, focusing on ways that FLW reduction can be integrated into the corporate governance framework and strategies (v) gender-specific brief, focusing on how gender issues should be taken onboard FLW policies. The policy briefs will be used as the basis of advocacy activities at the EU, and Member State levels, through events & bilateral online meetings.</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presenting the integral, extended versions of the EU Policy Briefs, adapted to fit the deliverable format and requirements (Chapter 3). - Discussing the potential for use and dissemination of the EU Policy Briefs, including areas for further policy development and advocacy windows. Completed dissemination activities are highlighted (Chapter 4).

Table 2: Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The ZeroW project supports the objectives of the Farm to Fork (F2F) Strategy and the European Green Deal to halve per capita food waste at retail and consumer stages by 2030. By the project end in 2025, the consortium aims to achieve a 20% reduction in retail food waste and a 25% reduction at consumer level through the Systemic Innovation Living Labs. In the medium term to 2030, ZeroW seeks to contribute to a 50% reduction in per capita food waste at retail and consumer levels, and in the long term to 2050 it aims for a near zero per capita outcome.

Deliverable D8.1 established the state of play of food loss and waste in the European Union and set out a trend pathway for reduction using a systemic, whole chain perspective. It developed three forward looking pathways that apply innovative and sustainable practices to prevent or eliminate waste across the food supply chain, each implying different degrees of policy change, technological innovation and consumer behaviour shift. This work drew on engagement with stakeholders through working groups and interviews to identify the drivers of waste generation and the levers for reduction.

Building on this foundation, Deliverable D8.2 refined the three transition scenarios using economic simulations from WP1 Task 1.3. Findings were validated in roundtable discussions with stakeholders from across the food supply chain to assess feasibility and implications. The report also integrates a targeted literature review on a just pathway for food loss and waste reduction, complemented by partner deliberation within WP8 and feedback from external stakeholders. The result is a set of just and realistic intermediate targets consistent with a pathway to near zero food loss and waste by 2050, with clear links to the interventions being developed in the ZeroW Living labs and the identification of seven “Just Pathway Actions” that outline crucial areas of intervention for more specific recommendations.

In this final Deliverable D8.3, we aim to finalise this process by presenting five EU Policy Briefs that were developed based on the insights and results of T8.1 and T8.2. This report revisits the methodology and approach of WP8, providing the conceptual rationale and policy context of the briefs. The extended EU Policy Briefs published in September 2025 are subsequently set out in full, followed by a discussion of their intended use and dissemination, including priorities for further policy development and associated advocacy windows.

This deliverable is constructed in five key chapters:

- **Chapter 1** sets out the context for this report, as detailed in Sections 1.1 to 1.3.
- **Chapter 2** revisits the WP8 approach and the T8.2 methodology, notably the conceptualisation of a just pathway and the just and realistic intermediate

food waste reduction targets, and situates the briefs within the wider policy context, including the progress and completion of the Waste Framework Directive revision.

- **Chapter 3** presents the full extended versions of the EU Policy Briefs, adapted to the format and requirements of this deliverable; the content is identical to the online versions, and the extended format was selected for its depth and explicit cross references to T8.2.
- **Chapter 4** discusses intended use and dissemination, including priorities for further policy development and associated advocacy windows.
- **Chapter 5** provides concise conclusions on the development of the policy briefs.

2. The WP8 approach: grounded policy recommendations

2.1 Building on the methodology and insights of T8.2

In T8.2, we identified just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets for the year 2030. These targets represent the project's final recommendation on the development of the Waste Framework Directive revision and the requirements of the F2F Action Plan. They are the result of a careful analysis based on the following elements: 1) The economic modelling results of three policy pathway scenarios developed in T8.1; 2) a conceptual framework and literature review centred around the definition of a "just pathway" and 3) direct feedback from stakeholders across the Food Supply Chain (FSC) who were engaged in roundtable discussions and interviews.

The ZeroW Policy team's conceptualisation of a *just pathway* from D8.2 implies *a transition to a more sustainable, fair and inclusive food system - reducing environmental impact in the short term, fostering economic growth in the medium term, and strengthening resilience against climate change in the long term*. To address the recognised shortcomings of the F2F Strategy, which fails to address the social dimensions of food and propel a truly transformative and socially just food policy, this definition was based on three core dimensions of 'justice' in the food system: *distributional* (identifying who bears the cost of the transition and who enjoys the benefits); *procedural* (the narrative of blame towards certain members of the FSC); *recognition* (acknowledging where inequalities cannot be addressed and compensating the affected stakeholders accordingly) (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2; Jackson et al., 2021; European Environment Agency, 2023).

The results of the economic modelling simulations (Pijpers and Drabik, 2025; Bartelings and Gatto, 2025) and the direct stakeholder feedback gathered in dedicated roundtable sessions were analysed and contextualised in this framework

of a 'just pathway'. The analysis highlighted the need to include vulnerable groups in the just transition to near-zero FLW by 2050 and identified the following intermediate targets as the most feasible and realistic for 2030:

Food waste reduction target on	Mandatory 2030 FW reduction target	Voluntary 2030 FW reduction target
Primary production	n/a	10%
Processing & Manufacturing	10% (absolute amount in mass units)	For higher target levels
Retail & Consumption	30% (per capita)	For higher target levels

Table 3: Final proposal for just and realistic intermediate FLW reduction targets (2030) (ZeroW Deliverable D8.2, 2025)

The choice of these specific targets is linked to the simulations and analysis of the three policy pathways, considering a more adequate and balanced combination of their suggested targets. The full details are available in D8.2. The analysis considers negative repercussions and potential environmental spillovers identified in the simulations, which would render more ambitious targets neither just nor feasible by 2030.

The chosen targets align with those of the European Commission's original proposal for the revision of the Waste Framework Directive and the final agreement between the Council and the European Parliament. They represent a balanced approach that considers current capabilities while maintaining an ambitious direction for the future. In the analysis, two findings stand out: 1) EU policymakers could also re-evaluate and prioritise other approaches such as waste revalorisation and 2) even the achievement of these chosen balanced targets is highly dependent on addressing crucial needed actions and areas of intervention.

The analysis in D8.2 pointed out several crucial trade-offs and potential unintended consequences of waste reduction measures in different scenarios. On the basis of direct stakeholder feedback and the simulation results, the ZeroW Policy Team identified the following seven "Just Pathway Actions" (see Figure 4). While not exhaustive, these priority actions outline the measures needed to progress toward a truly just pathway; addressing them comprehensively would increase the likelihood of meeting the proposed 2030 targets. Most importantly, these actions underline the need for a hybrid approach because there is no straightforward, one-size-fits-all approach that can effectively address all concerns. This is a crucial insight for policymakers, as these actions may also inform the strategy and design of the national action plans that Member States are now required to implement to meet the newly binding reduction targets (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2).

Figure 4: Overview of the Just Pathway Actions (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2)

The workshop discussions and reflections in T8.2 enabled the ZeroW policy team to map key gaps and areas needing more specific policy guidance, illustrated by the seven Just Pathway Actions. Aligned with ongoing debates and policy developments, these actions form the conceptual and practical basis for targeted short- and medium-term recommendations, with a call to embed these objectives in policymaking as a priority. Consequently, these actions served as guiding considerations to inform and thus shape the development of five EU Policy Briefs.

2.2 The conceptual rationale and policy context of the EU Policy Briefs

I. The completion and achievement of the Waste Framework Directive Revision

The evolving policy landscape has directly shaped the activities delivered under WP8. The proposed revision of the Waste Framework Directive sits within the European Commission's F2F Strategy and the European Green Deal. Its objective is to accelerate a fair, healthy, and environmentally sustainable food system by reducing food waste across the supply chain.

Trilogue negotiations between the European Commission, the European Parliament, and the Council concluded on 19 February 2025 with a provisional political agreement that introduces binding national food waste reduction targets to be met by 31 December 2030 (European Commission, 2025). The agreed targets are:

- Primary production: no target;
- Processing and manufacturing: reduction by 10% against a 2021–2023 baseline;
- Retail and consumption: joint per capita reduction by 30% across retail, restaurants, food services, and households.

This outcome contrasts with the Parliament's position adopted in March 2024, which sought more ambitious percentage reductions, namely 20% for processing and manufacturing and 40% for retail and consumption, while maintaining no target for primary production (European Parliament, 2024). As outlined in the previous section, the targets identified by the policy team in T8.2 are aligned with the final legislative outcome of the trilogue negotiations.

On 10 September 2025, the amended Directive was published, representing a major turning point in EU food waste policy. For the first time, binding and measurable EU-level food waste reduction targets have been introduced, moving beyond the previous framework of high-level encouragement and voluntary commitments. These targets are accompanied by harmonised measurement obligations, ensuring that all countries use comparable methods when tracking progress, and by mandatory public reporting. Moreover, the establishment of a mid-term review in 2027 creates an opportunity to strengthen or recalibrate the targets should early results fall short. Importantly, food waste has also been incorporated into the EU's early-warning system, which increases transparency and introduces a mechanism for public accountability if Member States lag behind.

While these advances are widely recognised as a significant policy achievement, debates persist around their adequacy and feasibility. From one perspective, the amended WFD creates, for the first time, a common baseline and shared trajectory across Europe. It signals a clear political recognition that food waste reduction is no longer optional, but an enforceable obligation with concrete metrics. However, concerns remain that the level of ambition is still too modest. The 30% reduction target falls short of the 50% reduction by 2030 required under Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 12.3, and without stronger enforcement mechanisms, progress may remain uneven across Member States. Critics also point to the need to enact structural changes needed to prevent food waste in the first place, especially considering the fragmented nature of the food supply chain (Marsden et al., 2018).

Therefore, the WFD revision provides both an achievement to be celebrated and an advocacy window to be seized. The legal framework is now in place, but the crucial challenge is to make the targets reachable in practice. This requires not only better governance and harmonised monitoring but also systemic interventions that reshape incentives and behaviours across the supply chain. A wider food system transformation constitutes the foundational basis of the 'just pathway' conceptualised in T8.2. It offers a unique opportunity to use ZeroW results to ensure that the objectives of the Directive are met through innovative tools, evidence-based policy advice, and collaborative solutions that connect prevention with practical

action. The ZeroW recommendations can influence both target achievement and the means by which it is realised.

II. Addressing identified gaps: debates and advocacy opportunities

The adoption of the revised WFD in September 2025 marked a turning point. Yet debates remain over how these targets will be achieved, leaving space for continued advocacy and constructive engagement in their implementation.

The ZeroW policy briefs aim to bridge this gap by focusing on key pressure points in the food system. Drawing from the results of T8.2 these EU Policy Briefs focus on four main areas: (i) actor-specific policies, focusing on consumers and farmers; (ii) food chain structure, focusing on short food supply chains; (iii) governance, examining ways that FLW reduction can be better integrated into governance frameworks and strategies; and (iv) context specific policies, centred on the urban environment. These areas of intervention were chosen based on their centrality to systemic change and the insights emerging from ZeroW economic modelling, stakeholder engagement, and Living Lab activities.

The selected intervention areas for the policy briefs align with ongoing debates and advocacy opportunities concerning the need to reform the food system, while identifying additional topics and leverage points for deeper exploration. For this purpose, it is also relevant to look at the EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste, which has created several thematic sub-groups that gather practitioners from business, civil society, academia, and public authorities. These include the *Action & implementation sub-group*, *Consumer food waste prevention sub-group*, *Food donation sub-group*, *Food loss and waste monitoring sub-group* (European Commission, 2025k). These sub-groups collect grounded insights from stakeholders running interventions across Europe. Their discussions reveal both the opportunities and frictions that arise when policies meet practice and therefore provide a valuable lens to understand ongoing debates and advocacy dynamics.

In many EU countries, a significant share of food waste occurs at the consumer level, within households, restaurants, and retail, often resulting from habits, limited information, and structural inefficiencies, making it a central focus of both ZeroW recommendations and practitioner debate. The ZeroW Policy Team highlighted the policy problem that current awareness and information campaigns have had only limited impact, underscoring the need for more targeted consumer incentives and stronger policy support for social innovation (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2). Achieving the new targets depends critically on everyday behaviours such as meal planning, food storage, and the correct interpretation of date labels. Without clear communication, accessible guidance, and supportive infrastructure, households may struggle to contribute meaningfully to the reductions envisaged. Thus, addressing household food waste requires recognising the behavioural dimension,

which is too often overlooked in innovation strategies and in the design of R&I projects. A shift in how food waste is framed and understood is essential, providing the foundation for policies that are paired with meaningful social innovations. Feedback from the *Consumer food waste prevention sub-group* similarly stressed that awareness alone is insufficient and that interventions must be designed to be supportive, practical, and audience-specific (European Commission, 2025g). This creates opportunities for a policy commitment that goes beyond short-term campaigns and supports long-term, behaviourally informed interventions with stable funding.

Moreover, the ZeroW Policy Team identified persistent food loss at the farm primary production stage as a critical policy problem. While EU attention to this issue has increased, results from ZeroW show that reductions in food waste can create unintended environmental spillovers, such as higher emissions in primary agriculture linked to intensified production and fertiliser use (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2). At the same time, small-scale farmers face structural barriers such as limited access to infrastructure, finance, fair markets, and digital tools, alongside weak enforcement of protections against unfair trading practices (Directive 2019/633). Without targeted interventions to overcome these inequalities, food loss strategies risk worsening disparities and generating new environmental harms, rather than contributing to a just and sustainable transition.

Building on these crucial gaps, the policy team developed a separate brief focusing on Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs), which have emerged in recent research as an opportunity to reduce losses by shortening logistics and improving traceability, while fostering closer producer-consumer relationships (Voge et al., 2023). The advocacy opportunity lies in developing policy frameworks that *actively* support SFSCs. This includes incentives for participation, funding for infrastructure and digitalisation, and regulatory guidance on transparency and data sharing. By integrating SFSCs into broader EU food waste strategies, policymakers can leverage their potential to reduce losses while promoting a more inclusive and sustainable food system.

To operationalise such a transformation of the food system itself, a coherent governance framework is needed. However, debates around governance point to important tensions that policymakers must consider. In the current status quo, food loss and waste levels remain high in the absence of a coherent governance framework that guarantees transparency, accountability, and coordination across the food supply chain (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2). For instance, companies are not systematically required to measure or report waste, while existing policies offer few incentives for prevention, data sharing, or collaboration. Therefore, meeting EU reduction targets within a just transition demands stronger governance that enforces transparent reporting, rewards effective action, and promotes inclusive,

co-created solutions across the chain. Here, advocacy opportunities centre on ensuring that governance frameworks both reward prevention and embed transparent monitoring, while also balancing technological and social innovations, as discussed in the *Action and implementation sub-group* (European Commission, 2025h). Moreover, a relevant area of governance opportunities concerns data collection and monitoring frameworks, as discussed in the *Monitoring sub-group* (European Commission, 2025i). A key insight is the need to balance accuracy and practicality in measurement. Monitoring should go beyond measuring waste quantities to assess inclusiveness and systemic impact, for instance by tracking the participation of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), schools, or minority-led initiatives in urban food waste programmes.

Finally, urban governance introduces another critical site of contestation. Urban FLW policies remain constrained by fragmented governance, limited municipal capacity, and power imbalances that sideline smaller actors and vulnerable groups (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2). While cities are uniquely positioned to connect stakeholders and drive systemic change, they often lack the mandate, tools, and resources to scale effective interventions. For instance, municipalities engage in food redistribution and procurement schemes, but their efforts are undermined by limited mandates and inconsistent links to national strategies. Discussions in the *Food donation sub-group* confirm this potential and expose these barriers: liability rules for donors remain unclear, redistribution is constrained by strict traceability and labelling requirements, and local actors often lack the resources to implement solutions (European Commission, 2025j). Advocacy opportunities lie in pressing for clearer regulatory frameworks for donation, recognition of municipalities in national food waste plans, and greater fiscal support to scale promising local innovations.

While these areas form the backbone of the project's advocacy strategy, they do not exhaust the field. Moreover, the decision not to develop a stand-alone gender-specific policy brief, although foreseen in the task description, reflects a deliberate choice to embed gender considerations across all briefs rather than isolate them in a separate document. This approach ensures that gender equity is treated as an integral dimension of the just transition, embedded within the analyses of consumer behaviour, farming practices, governance and supply chain structures, and urban policies, rather than as an add-on topic.

Taken together, the five policy briefs constitute a coherent roadmap for achieving the intermediate 2030 targets and guiding the transition towards near-zero food loss and waste by 2050. They demonstrate that this goal is attainable if action is coordinated across all levels of the food system, underpinned by fairness, inclusivity, and resilience.

The next chapter presents the content of the five EU Policy Briefs. Each brief examines in greater depth the intricacies, challenges and opportunities highlighted

in this section and translates them into actionable options. Dissemination has been ongoing since September 2025 through relevant events, conferences, and meetings, as set out in Chapter 4.

3. The five ZeroW EU Policy Briefs

This chapter presents the extended versions of the policy briefs. They explore the selected topics in depth and provide clear cross references to the work undertaken in T8.2 and reported in D8.2. To maximise dissemination, shorter, more concise versions are available online on the [SAFE website](#). In this chapter, the policy briefs have been adapted to the appropriate format and referencing style of a project deliverable.

POLICY BRIEF: BUILDING CONSUMER CAPACITY FOR A JUST ZERO FOOD WASTE TRANSITION

Introduction

In many EU countries, a substantial portion of food waste occurs at the consumer level - within households, restaurants, and retail environments - driven by behavioural habits, inadequate information, and structural inefficiencies. The transition towards near-zero food waste in our food systems must be aligned with the principles of the Fair Transition and the European Pillar of Social Rights, ensuring that consumers, particularly those facing economic constraints and knowledge gaps are supported rather than disadvantaged. Systemic barriers disproportionately affect the most vulnerable consumer groups.

The ZeroW Policy Team identified a 'Just Transition Pathway', which recognises these inequalities and fosters enabling environments that prioritise practical solutions, promote behavioural change, and safeguard social inclusion. In addition, consumers should neither be blamed nor sidelined in the just transition towards a near-zero FLW food system. For EU policymakers, reducing food waste among consumers presents a high-impact opportunity to lower greenhouse gas emissions, alleviate pressure on food systems, and advance sustainability and climate goals.

This focus has become even more critical in light of the provisional agreement reached on 19 February 2025 during trilogue negotiations on the revision of the Waste Framework Directive (WFD) between the European Commission, the European Parliament, and the Council. Notably, the agreement includes the world's first legally binding national targets for food waste reduction, to be achieved by 31 December 2030 (Council of the European Union, 2025). These legislative developments underscore the urgency for Member States to develop and implement effective national action plans that place consumers at the centre of food

waste reduction strategies. This policy brief outlines evidence-based recommendations to help governments create enabling environments that support consumer awareness, incentivise behaviour change, and build more efficient food systems with the EU's Just Transition, which will guide the action plans of Member States for the newly adopted binding targets.

Policy Problem

As household food waste comprises the largest share of food waste in the EU, a relevant approach to consumers should be prioritised in the just transition. The ZeroW Policy Team identified the limited effectiveness of current awareness and information campaigns, reiterating the need for more targeted consumer incentives and a greater policy emphasis on social innovation. The behavioural aspect, often overlooked in innovation development, is crucial to tackle household food waste. This begins with reframing how food waste is perceived and understood, forming the basis for policy interventions coupled with meaningful social innovation.

Evidence from Project

To achieve a just and fair transition toward near-zero FLW by 2050, practical solutions that support consumer engagement and behavioural change must be prioritised. Such change needs to be embedded within broader systemic reforms, which are essential to transform current food systems and market dynamics. A crucial aspect of this shift, emphasised in Deliverable D8.2's literature review, involves moving beyond the perception of food as a tradable commodity (i.e., valued for traits such as shelf life, visual appeal, and standardisation) and instead recognising it as a fundamental good, with intrinsic nutritional, cultural, and social value.

Reframing how food is valued also necessitates rethinking the notion of food waste, challenging the perceived "convenience" of discarding food, and fostering the revalorisation of surplus and discarded food. This shift should form part of a broader behavioural and societal transformation. The importance of this 'mindset change' was reiterated by several different stakeholders in roundtable working groups organised by the ZeroW Policy Team, as they emphasised that while technological innovations are valuable in addressing food system challenges and lowering abatement costs, fostering a shift in mindset is equally important. Cultural norms and social behaviours related to food disposal play a critical role and demand interventions that go beyond technological fixes. This is where the Just Pathway Action 5 "Targeted Consumer Incentives" from the ZeroW Deliverable D8.2 becomes particularly relevant (see Figure 4). The ZeroW roundtable discussions and simulation results underscore that consumer behaviour - though complex and slow to shift - is essential to achieving FLW reduction targets. Behavioural change needs

to be recognised as both a social and policy challenge, requiring tailored incentives and enabling environments.

Financial incentives for low-income households to adopt food-saving practices - tax credits for food-saving apps, rebates on smart storage tools, or free compost collection services - can make a significant impact, particularly given that household food waste represents the largest share of total FLW in the EU. Other European projects like CHORIZO highlight the need to empower consumers by translating good intentions into practical action, through supportive environments and hands-on guidance.

Technological innovations, such as the smart packaging for fresh fish being developed in SILL2, exhibited the need for consumer guidance and support to address issues like neophobia and build trust in new food packaging practices fighting food waste. Providing targeted support is essential to foster consumer acceptance. Hence, the behavioural dimension should not be decoupled from technological innovation, and consumers' perspectives should be considered when designing new research projects. EU policymakers should incorporate this approach into the design of more targeted consumer-focused engagement strategies and interventions. Hence, these findings guide the following policy recommendations.

Key Policy Recommendations

Drawing on the research and findings of the ZeroW project, this set of specific policy recommendations is designed to enhance consumer engagement and implement targeted interventions, all within the framework of a just transition toward near-zero food waste in our food systems.

1. Implement data-driven, consumer-centric interventions, and more targeted consumer engagement

Consumer-oriented strategies are essential to reducing household food waste and policymakers should prioritise them in their action plans.

Educational initiatives and information campaigns should improve when targeting schools, community centres, and workplaces. These should highlight the environmental and economic impacts of food waste, while addressing how cultural norms and social behaviours influence consumptions and disposal practices. Examples include integrating mandatory educational modules into school curricula, launching community education programmes focused on practical skills for waste reduction, such as Hungary's project "Wasteless", a comprehensive national programme combining formal education and community workshops, focusing on circular-economy cooking and bilingual school materials.

Activities include school-based lessons on zero-waste cooking, home preservation techniques, and waste audits. Since 2016, the training has been

delivered to approximately 35000 students and 1900 teachers. Embedding these activities directly into school curricula has already proven successful, as the project reached approximately 27% quantifiable reductions in avoidable household food waste and significantly strengthened consumer capacity to apply practical skills at home (Interreg Europe, 2025). These actions align with the ZeroW stakeholders' priorities that place waste prevention measures at the forefront.

Dynamic consumer engagement models are needed to move beyond traditional awareness campaigns, by using interactive and participatory methods such as gamification. Inspiring examples include “No Scrap Left Behind”, a gamified in-store campaign that used trivia and prize-based visual prompts to encourage consumer action (Wong et al., 2021). This typology of game achieved micro behavioural changes even without heavy monetary incentives. Such successful demonstrations of engagement should be further supported and promoted.

Other dynamic engagement models include peer-driven community challenges, such as the “Campus Race to Zero Waste” competition from the United States. Universities compete on reducing total waste, including food waste. The organisers take advantage of inter-university rivalries, peer sharing, and public recognition incentives to stimulate collective action and shared responsibility (Campus Race to Zero Waste, 2024). Moreover, social media-driven behavioural nudges should not be underestimated.

Annual or seasonal social media campaigns have the potential to reach millions of people and spark considerable change. An example is the Zero Waste Week, an award-winning, grassroots annual awareness campaign originally started in the UK, which now takes place online and on-the-ground, directly helping householders, businesses, and organisations reduce landfill waste (Zero Waste Week, 2025). The strong impact and broad reach of this grassroots campaign should serve as a catalyst for the expansion of similar initiatives, ideally backed by proactive support and endorsement from policymakers.

Fiscal incentives retain a crucial importance for consumers, for instance implementing targeted tax credits or direct subsidies to encourage concrete interventions to support households, particularly among low-income populations. Examples include subsidies for purchasing food storage solutions such as smart fridge sensors or vacuum storage systems and promoting usage of food-saving mobile applications, like those piloted in SILL9.

Fiscal incentives can go hand in hand with inclusive technological solutions, implementing incentives to adopt technology-driven solutions, such as providing discounted smart storage technologies including mobile apps for sensor-based storage units designed to reduce food waste. It is imperative to ensure that these tools are accessible by offering features suitable for users with varying digital literacy. This includes simplified user interfaces, multilingual guides, or voice-

command functionality for those less confident with digital devices. Gender-specific barriers should be addressed by providing inclusive training sessions - for example, workshops specifically designed for women entrepreneurs or consumers - to build digital skills and confidence. Diverse user groups should be actively involved (including women, elderly, and rural communities) in the technology design and implementation process. This approach helps to create practical, culturally relevant technologies responsive to genuine user needs. In the context of a Just Transition, vulnerable groups should be prioritised to ensure equitable access for all.

2. Foster social innovation and reframe food waste perceptions

Effective reduction of food waste requires consumer-focused strategies that recognise and address behavioural dynamics. A good starting point would be further encouraging social innovation by supporting community-driven projects that shift perceptions of food waste from purely environmental concerns to moral and community responsibilities. Campaigns should emphasise positive impacts such as community solidarity, economic savings, and improved food security.

Vulnerable consumers must be protected, creating targeted interventions ensuring vulnerable groups, especially lower-income households, benefit equitably from innovative waste reduction solutions. Incentives should be designed with inclusion in mind by ensuring offline access, providing support for digitally excluded populations, and maintaining the accessibility and affordability of healthy food options.

Behavioural integration with technological innovation should be prioritised, reinforcing the linkage between technological innovations (e.g., smart fridges, smart packaging for fresh food products) and behavioural aspects through comprehensive training, personalised feedback systems, and support networks. Another important way to make these linkages is by including distinct target groups (e.g., women, people of varying age categories, and with varying degrees of digital literacy) in the design process of the solution. Trust building campaigns are essential and should be tailored to different cultural contexts and user preferences. Fostering data sharing between consumers and supermarkets, as outlined in SILL9, can further enhance collaboration and improve FLW reduction at household and retail levels.

Throughout the entire process, guidance should be action-oriented, providing clear, actionable, and practical guidelines that translate consumer willingness into concrete behavioural changes, emphasising ease, convenience, and immediate benefits which will sustain stakeholders interest and engagement. Examples include effective food storage, mindful shopping practices, meal planning, and creative food reuse through various accessible media platforms. Drawing from the experience and results of SILL2, this guidance must be designed to align with

innovations addressing consumer perceptions to foster widespread adoption and success (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2).

3. Incentivising urban consumers to reduce food waste through local policy initiatives

To effectively engage urban populations, policies should prioritise:

- **Local policy initiatives:** Foster urban-specific policies, such as city-based incentive programmes rewarding reduced household waste measured through municipal waste audits.
- **Community-level innovations:** Encourage municipal-led initiatives like community refrigerators, neighbourhood composting programmes, and local food-sharing platforms. Policy incentives could include grants or municipal recognition for high-performing communities.
- **Economic and practical incentives:** Implement economic benefits like reduced waste collection fees for households or communities demonstrably reducing their food waste footprint (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2).
- **Collaborative frameworks:** Facilitate collaboration between local authorities, businesses, and NGOs to create cohesive local food waste reduction ecosystems. Promote partnerships with retailers and restaurants for donation systems and waste reduction collaborations. Collaborative frameworks should be built on collective policymaking, ensuring active contributions from all stakeholders in the design, development, and implementation of FLW reduction solutions.
- **Local capacity building:** Invest in capacity building through local workshops and training sessions designed to equip urban consumers with skills and knowledge needed for effective food waste management practices.

Conclusion

Achieving a near-zero FLW future in the EU by 2050, now underpinned by legally binding national targets, demands more than technological innovation or general awareness campaigns. As evidenced by the ZeroW project and reinforced through stakeholder engagement and simulation results, the most effective path forward places consumers at the core of systemic change.

Household food waste remains the largest contributor to overall FLW in the EU, and current interventions have proven insufficient. Addressing this challenge requires a multidimensional approach that integrates behavioural insight, targeted fiscal and technological incentives, inclusive policy design, and social innovation. Crucially, efforts need to move beyond treating food waste as a matter of individual responsibility and instead foster enabling environments that shift cultural norms, redefine the value of food, and close equity gaps - particularly for low-income and digitally excluded populations.

POLICY BRIEF: EMPOWERING FARMERS FOR A JUST ZERO FOOD WASTE TRANSITION

Introduction

As Europe needs to move toward more resilient and resource-efficient food systems, reducing primary production losses has become a policy imperative. FLW reduction in primary production is deeply interconnected with broader structural, economic, and technological dynamics, making it necessary to pursue a systemic and just transition that prioritises farmers' needs, especially those of smallholders and marginalised groups. This policy brief outlines evidence-based recommendations to help governments create enabling environments that support farmers in the EU's Just Transition, which will guide the action plans of Member States for the newly adopted binding targets.

Policy Problem

Despite growing policy attention, food loss at the primary production stage continues to persist across EU Member States. The MAGNET analysis General Equilibrium Model carried out during the project (which captures the effects of FLW reduction measures on the whole economic system) uncovered significant environmental spillovers.

While reducing FLW lowers greenhouse gas emissions in waste management, it may counterintuitively result in increased emissions in primary agriculture and non-food sectors. This unintended consequence arises from the intensified agricultural production needed to meet higher food demand and affordability, particularly for commodities with high FLW rates, alongside increased use of chemical fertilisers. Moreover, small-scale farmers face multiple barriers that prevent them from engaging in or benefiting from FLW-reducing innovations. These include limited access to infrastructure, finance, fair markets, and digital technologies. The persistent digital divide, weak enforcement of protections against unfair trading practices (EU Directive 2019/633), and lack of tailored support mechanisms reinforce structural inequalities in the food system. Without targeted policy interventions that address these interconnected challenges, FLW strategies risk exacerbating existing disparities and generating new environmental harms, rather than delivering the just and sustainable transformation that EU policies envision.

Evidence from Project

Economic modelling simulations from the ZeroW project showcased that, regardless of the measures applied, reducing FLW with innovations leads to great efficiency and higher output. While this contributes to food security, the rebound effect,

manifested as increased agricultural production, can drive up land use and input intensity, with potentially ecological consequences. As production becomes more efficient and losses decrease, total output tends to rise, especially for loss intensive commodities that benefit most from these gains. It results in biodiversity loss and heightened greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from both the agricultural and non-food sectors, largely due to increased use of chemical fertilisers and growing demand for non-food goods. Additionally, the use of AI-based innovations could also generate environmental spillovers. This highlights the urgent need to pair FLW reduction strategies with investments in sustainable agricultural practices.

The literature review conducted during the project emphasises the importance of shortening supply chains through mechanisms like public food infrastructure, farmers' markets, and Community Supported Agriculture (CSA). These localised systems not only reduce waste by minimising logistical inefficiencies but also promote fair pricing, support agroecological transitions, and build producer resilience to market shocks and climate change.

Digital tools play a vital role in optimising production, improve traceability, and enhancing market access. However, a persistent digital divide, rooted in poor connectivity, limited digital literacy, and high costs, prevents many smallholder and vulnerable farmers from reaping these benefits. This divide creates a 'trolley dilemma': while digital innovations can enhance food production and reduce losses, they risk exacerbating inequalities and undermining environmental goals if access is not equitably distributed. Bridging this gap requires coordinated investment in infrastructure, inclusive training programs, and cooperative data-sharing models.

Insights from the ZeroW SILLs and Just Pathway Action 3 underscore the critical role of horizontal peer learning and data sharing in scaling successful innovations across different agricultural contexts (see Figure 4). Access to reliable, interoperable data is essential for effective implementation, monitoring, and impact measurement of FLW interventions. Shared platforms and trust-based data governance models, such as those granting farmers control over their own information, are essential to foster cooperation and innovation adoption at scale. SILL 5 - and production-focused innovations more broadly - highlighted two key challenges: first, securing acceptance of the solution from producers; and second, facilitating effective data sharing. In addition, it showed that technology alone will not be enough to improve the situation, requiring a system-wide approach.

Despite the EU Directive 2019/633 against unfair trading practices, enforcement remains weak, continuing to disadvantage producers in the FSC. Achieving near-zero FLW will require not just legal frameworks but sustained investment, including subsidised waste reduction technologies and community-based solutions.

SILLs results highlight the importance of government-supported grants and long-term financial mechanisms to facilitate innovation, especially among vulnerable and small-scale producers. Just Pathway Action 4 identifies collaborative investment models, such as shared machinery or joint digital platforms, as effective tools to lower barriers to innovation and resource efficiency (see Figure 4). These approaches are particularly impactful when aligned with targeted vocational training and support for knowledge development. Hence, these findings guide the following policy recommendations.

Key Policy Recommendations

Farmers, positioned at the forefront of efforts to create more sustainable food systems, face a direct intersection between climate action and FLW reduction. These vectors are closely linked: both aim to lower GHG emissions and depend on access to timely, actionable data to guide sustainable farming practices. Moreover, reducing FLW contributes to climate resilience by supporting more efficient food systems and easing pressure on ecosystems and natural resources. The remainder of this brief therefore outlines key recommendations that simultaneously advance climate objectives and FLW reduction goals.

1. Enhance farmers' resilience to climate change through sustainable practices

1.1. Accelerate adoption of Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA)

Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) offers a strategic framework for transforming food systems in response to climate change. Defined by the FAO, CSA aims to achieve three interlinked goals: enhancing agricultural productivity and incomes sustainably, building resilience to climate change, and lowering or eliminating GHG emissions where feasible (FAO, 2025a). Its broad scope encompasses both low-tech and high-tech solutions, adaptable to local conditions and capacities. CSA includes a wide array of traditional and ecologically grounded practices that require minimal technological input. These include:

- **Soil Health Improvements:** Practices such as composting, mulching, and crop rotation help maintain soil fertility and reduce dependence on synthetic inputs.
- **Efficient water use:** Techniques like drip irrigation and rainwater harvesting enhance water-use efficiency, especially in drought-prone regions.
- **Climate-resilient crops:** Selecting and cultivating crop varieties adapted to shifting local climate conditions helps safeguard yields.

These methods contribute to both mitigation and productivity. For example, reducing the use of chemical fertilisers and avoiding practices like soil compaction can cut methane emissions and support carbon sequestration through perennial cropping (FAO, 2025b).

Advanced digital and technological tools can amplify the impact of CSA, improving decision-making and reducing environmental footprints. One key example is precision farming, a data-driven management approach that uses sensors, GPS, and real-time analytics to respond to variability in crop and livestock systems (European Commission, 2025a). This can lead to higher yields and resource efficiency as well as reduced environmental pressures, such as excessive fertiliser use or water waste, among other benefits. Moreover, digital technologies can support climate adaptation through better risk management. Sensor networks, for instance, enable early detection of extreme weather events like droughts, informing both individual decisions and public interventions, such as drought early warning systems and improved water governance (OECD, 2019).

Another systematic approach to rural resilience is the Smart Villages concept, promoted by the European Network for Rural Development (ENRD). It reflects a holistic approach to strengthening rural communities. By integrating digital tools with participatory governance, smart villages foster innovation, improve service delivery, and enhance local economies. This model not only supports CSA but also helps reverse rural decline by making villages more liveable, economically vibrant and self-sustaining.

Nonetheless, this process must be approached with great care, prioritising societal well-being, climate resilience, food security, and the sustainable use of natural resources. Importantly, farmers who choose not to adopt digital technologies should have their decisions respected and be supported through alternative means, recognising the diversity of contexts and needs in agriculture.

1.2. Mobilise policy support to enable CSA implementation

Promoting the adoption of CSA practices requires a comprehensive policy framework that addresses financial, technical, and informational barriers. A just and effective transition hinges on ensuring that CSA options are accessible and feasible for all actors in the agrifood system, both large and small-scale farmers (European Commission, 2025b).

Direct funding is essential, particularly where CSA practices may initially lack cost efficiency. Instruments such as the eco-schemes under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP 2023-27) offer vital financial incentives (European Commission, 2025c). These schemes reward the adoption of practices that reduce environmental and climate impacts while promoting the transition to more sustainable farming models. Importantly, such incentives support the provision of public goods, such as biodiversity, clean water, and carbon sequestration, that are not adequately priced by market mechanisms. In addition, the CAP 2023-2027 includes provisions for rural development, including funding for the design and implementation of Smart Villages strategies. These aim to revitalise rural areas

through innovation, improved connectivity, and inclusive community planning. Access to technical support is critical to ensure that innovations are effectively utilised and their regulatory framework is understood. Farm advisory services can play a pivotal role by helping farmers navigate digital systems, adopt greening practices, diversify income sources, and comply with regulatory frameworks. Such services are essential to making CSA practices practical, especially for farmers who may be less familiar with new technologies.

At the same time, with assistance or farm advisory services, the modernisation of the CAP administration can have a greater welcome among farmers, by showing them how to navigate the different digitised applications or pre-filled online forms and making them see the benefits: simplification of administrative procedures, reduce bureaucratic complexity, enhance efficiency, and accelerate payment transfers to beneficiaries (European Commission, 2024; OECD, 2019).

Beyond financial and technical support, facilitating knowledge exchange is essential. Governments should invest in networks that promote peer-to-peer learning and horizontal knowledge sharing. As highlighted in ZeroW Deliverable 8.2, not all farmers actively engage with centralised hubs or digital platforms. Therefore, outreach efforts must be proactive and tailored, ensuring that valuable information reaches farmers directly and in accessible formats.

1.3. Role of digital tools and innovation in resilience

The integration of digital technologies into agriculture might have the potential to transform the sector's capacity to withstand and adapt to economic, environmental, and social challenges (European Commission, 2024). By facilitating more informed decision-making, improving operational efficiency, and supporting sustainable practices, digital innovation, if well executed, might play a pivotal role in building resilience across the agri-food system. Digital platforms and precision agriculture tools enable farmers to access real-time data, monitor crop and soil conditions, and make evidence-based choices. This not only improves yields and resource efficiency but also contributes to long-term sustainability by minimising inputs and environmental impacts. Automation and smart machinery can ease the physical and mental demands of agricultural labour by reducing repetitive and strenuous tasks and thus creating more attractive working environments in rural areas.

2. Support small-scale farmers' digital transition

2.1. Build digital infrastructure and deliver training

Investing in digital and physical infrastructure is essential for advancing digitalisation, along with encouraging the reuse of existing assets. Three main pillars underpin effective infrastructure facilitation (OECD, 2019):

1. **Access to basic connectivity infrastructure:** This includes broadband and telecommunication services, which form the backbone of digital transformation.
2. **Range of data collection, storage, and analysis** through sensors, modelling, digital platforms, cloud solutions, and software systems.
3. **Supportive regulatory environment** also known as “soft infrastructure”. This refers to the institutional frameworks that establish interoperability standards, data quality norms, and regulations on data ownership and privacy (ibid.).

Governments play a crucial role across these pillars, acting as planners, enablers, investors, or regulators, depending on the maturity of existing infrastructure. For example, in regions where private investment is not viable, public investment in basic technologies like wireless sensor networks is necessary, creating opportunities for private sector collaboration. This underscores the importance of integrating all stakeholders and fostering public-private partnerships.

As regulators, governments must ensure that technologies used in commercial settings are properly validated and calibrated for policy or regulatory applications. Policymakers should also weigh the potential for increased regulatory burdens on farmers, especially since excessive compliance requirements can discourage technology adoption. Farmers are generally more receptive to technologies that offer operational benefits rather than those designed also to verify their regulatory compliance (ibid.).

Beyond infrastructure, targeted, hands-on, and in-person training is vital to address both the lack of awareness about digitalisation and the skills gap among farmers. Facilitating knowledge exchange through demonstration farms and familiar communication channels can significantly enhance technology uptake (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2). Such proactive training is particularly important for vulnerable groups, such as small-scale producers, who may not benefit sufficiently from online resources.

To boost participation in training, financial incentives or compensation should be provided, especially for workers displaced by automation in food production. Partnerships with industry leaders can help fund these initiatives (ibid.).

Training not only accelerates technology adoption but also promotes the generation of high-quality data by teaching best practices in data harmonisation, compatibility, and maintenance. This reduces the risk of poor management decisions based on inaccurate data or models in precision agriculture (OECD, 2019).

2.2. Promote the use of digital tools’ role in farm management efficiency and resource optimisation

Digital technologies significantly improve farm management by enabling precise monitoring and control of resources. These tools allow farmers to apply water, fertilisers, and pesticides with greater accuracy, minimising waste and environmental impact while boosting crop yields. Furthermore, by analysing both consumption (demand) and production (supply) data, digital solutions can help optimise crop planning, thereby reducing overproduction, surplus, and food loss. Digitalisation also enhances producers' ability to market their products by increasing their visibility to potential buyers. Notably, as Michel-Villarreal and co-authors emphasise, low-cost digital tools - including freeware and social media platforms - can be especially effective in connecting producers with markets, often playing a more significant role than anticipated (Michel-Villarreal et al. 2021). Digital technologies can also contribute to the development of rural areas by providing better accessibility and connections in line with the Long-Term Vision for the EU's Rural Areas (European Commission 2025d).

2.3. Bridging the digital divide among rural farming communities

While digitalisation presents major opportunities for improving agricultural efficiency and reducing food loss and waste, it also risks deepening existing inequalities. Many rural areas still struggle with unreliable or unaffordable internet access, and farmers - often older and with limited digital skills - face barriers such as high costs, geographic isolation, and weak connectivity. To ensure equitable access, digital tools, including application programming interfaces (APIs), must be user-friendly and designed around the expressed needs and capabilities of typical end-users.

To address these challenges and promote equitable access to data, information, and infrastructure - especially in rural areas facing issues like depopulation, limited services, and fewer economic opportunities - the CAP 2023-27 provides a supportive framework and funding for the adoption of innovative and smart solutions (European Commission 2025e).

Regional initiatives are also emerging to help close the digital gap. For example, the CreceA program in Andalusia, Spain, offers personalised, free advisory services to the agricultural sector (Junta de Andalucia, 2025). The initiative begins by assessing each farmer's situation and identifying their main challenges. Based on this assessment, a tailored action plan is developed, recommending specific digital solutions suited to each business' needs. Farmers and rural SMEs then receive individualised support throughout the digital transformation process, including assistance in securing public funding. In addition, a dedicated Technical and Support Office has been established to provide ongoing support to programme participants.

2.4. Address behavioural and gender barriers to digital adoption

While digitalisation in the primary production stage holds the promise of improving production efficiency, reducing FLW and enhancing rural livelihoods, its success hinges not only on technological readiness but also on behavioural, cultural, and social acceptance. Evidence from the SILLs highlights a recurring challenge: even when innovations are technically functional and capable of generating value, farmers often hesitate to adopt them due to usability concerns, uncertain benefits on the short and long term, lack of trust in data ownership arrangements, and fear of losing autonomy. These behavioural barriers are particularly acute for early adopters, who may bear higher burdens without immediate return on investment.

Beyond these general barriers, cultural, geographical, and gender-specific factors play a significant role in shaping digital uptake. The location of a farm, its size, crop type, and exposure to climate extremes, can either motivate adoption (e.g., to cope with unpredictable weather or labour shortages) or discourage it (e.g., in conflict adjacent zones like the Ukrainian border, where long-term investments feel riskier). Likewise, labour scarcity, particularly where cultural or policy resistance to migration exists, may prompt farmers to adopt automation and smart tools. Conversely, high-risk environments or instability can create reluctance toward adopting expensive, complex technologies.

Cultural norms around trust and authority also affect adoption dynamics (Quantifarm project) (European CAP Network, 2025). In more collectivist societies like Greece, Portugal, or Spain, farmers tend to trust people they know personally. In contrast, in more individualistic cultures like the Netherlands or Sweden, credibility is tied more to professional expertise. This has implications for the design of advisory and outreach strategies: in some regions, advisors need to act as embedded community members, while in others, they can function more independently. Tailoring engagement approaches to these trust patterns is essential for effective digital deployment.

Gender norms also influence uptake. In Southern and Eastern Europe, more traditional gender roles persist, which can result in the exclusion of women from technical decision-making even if they are the ones using digital technologies daily. In contrast, egalitarian gender norms which seem to be more prominent in Northern and Western Europe can facilitate women's access to digital tools and training. Therefore, it is critical to identify and directly engage the person, regardless of gender, who will actually operate or interact with the digital technologies. Failure to do so risks poor adoption outcomes and reinforces gender inequalities.

Addressing these behavioural and socio-cultural barriers requires a holistic, inclusive, and context-specific strategy. This includes investment in affordable infrastructure, provision of locally adapted training, co-creation of tools with intended and actual users, and fostering peer-to-peer knowledge exchange,

especially through trusted networks. Early adopters should be supported through visible, low-barrier benefits and local champions.

Even when all the constraints are overcome, there is still the possibility that farmers simply do not like the idea of digitalisation and prefer not to invest in it, and their decision should be respected. The digital transition must accommodate hybrid pathways and ensure that innovation does not come at the expense of farmer choice or cultural identity. This requires a flexible policy framework that promotes adoption without penalising non-participation, and that fosters a collaborative governance model to build trust, address liability concerns and clarify data ownership.

2.5. Ensure responsible data use, sharing, and innovation scalability

There are data sharing issues to address for the scalability of SILLs, including monitoring and measurement and horizontal peer learning. Ensuring the production of reliable, high-quality data - and guaranteeing its compatibility across digital tools and machinery - is essential for the scalability of agricultural technologies. Interoperability between different systems facilitates effective data sharing among private stakeholders and public authorities, which is crucial for monitoring, measurement, and horizontal peer learning. To address these needs, the European Commission has committed to developing a common European agricultural data space as part of its broader European data strategy (European Commission, 2025f).

Data security and privacy are also significant concerns, as some information may be considered personal or sensitive by farmers. Building trust is vital and can be supported by data governance models that give farmers control over their own data. For example, the Akkerweb Platform allows farmers exclusive access to their data, with the option to grant access to others as they choose (Wageningen University & Research, 2025). This “controlled access” approach helps foster a sense of security and encourages data sharing (OECD, 2019).

Conclusion

Reducing FLW at the primary production stage is both a strategic imperative and an opportunity for the EU to enact the Just Transition Pathway. Innovations from the ZeroW project clearly demonstrate that while FLW reduction can boost production efficiency and contribute to food availability, it must be pursued in tandem with robust safeguards against rebound effects, such as intensified input use and land expansion, that risk undermining environmental gains. Effective FLW strategies must prioritise system-wide approaches that integrate climate-smart agriculture, equitable digital transformation, and strengthened support for small-scale and vulnerable farmers. These strategies will only succeed if they are embedded in inclusive policy frameworks that address access to infrastructure, fair markets, and

knowledge. Investing in rural digital infrastructure, cooperative data sharing platforms, and horizontal learning networks will be critical to ensuring scalable, just, and sustainable innovation. Critically, these transitions must be participatory and farmer-centered. Respecting the diverse realities and preferences of farmers, particularly those who opt out of digitalisation, is essential to avoid deepening social divides. The tools and technologies promoted must be fit-for-purpose, easy to use, and responsive to the expressed needs of those they are intended to serve. These policy recommendations are necessary to reach a truly just transition in food systems, one that delivers environmental resilience, economic viability, and fairness for all farmers.

POLICY BRIEF: TRANSFORMING FOOD CHAIN STRUCTURE TO REDUCE FOOD LOSS AND WASTE (FLW)

Introduction

Reducing Food Loss and Waste (FLW) is a critical priority for achieving the goals of the European Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy, both of which aim to make food systems fairer, healthier, and more environmentally sustainable. This policy brief outlines key policy recommendations to shape the food value chain structure to prevent and reduce FLW, using technological, organisational, and governance innovations for a just transition pathway. It aims to support policymakers to reach the newly adopted binding food waste reduction targets, and in fostering digital and logistical innovations to transform the food chain structure and make it shorter, more resilient, and more sustainable.

Policy Problem

Despite the EU's strong commitment to reducing FLW under the Farm to Fork Strategy and Circular Economy Action Plan, current approaches remain mainly focused on technological and end-of-chain solutions (e.g., retail, consumer behaviour, waste management) while paying little attention to structural issues in the food supply chain. Specifically, the concentration of power in long, centralised food supply chains and insufficient support for resilient, short food supply chains (SFSCs) hinder systemic progress.

SFSCs are understood as systems where food production and consumption are geographically close and involve few or no intermediaries. Without targeted interventions to rebalance the food system structure, by investing in local food networks, logistics infrastructure, data interoperability, and equitable access to innovation, FLW reduction efforts may lead to unintended environmental and social consequences, such as increased agricultural emissions, biodiversity loss, and the exclusion of small-scale producers from new markets and technologies.

Evidence from Project

ZeroW provided critical insights into the structural challenges of the food chain and helped us develop targeted policy recommendations by combining advanced modelling, literature analysis, and real-world experimentation. Through a comprehensive approach, we were able to identify both systemic issues contributing to FLW and some necessary conditions for a just and effective transition.

The project carried out some general and partial equilibrium modelling analyses to shed light on the key spillovers in FLW reduction measures. The MAGNET analysis General Equilibrium Model (which captures the effects of FLW reduction measures on the whole economic system) uncovered significant environmental spillovers. While reducing FLW lowers greenhouse gas emissions in waste management, it may paradoxically result in increased emissions in primary agriculture and non-food sectors. This unintended consequence arises from the intensified agricultural production needed to meet higher food demand and affordability, particularly for commodities with high FLW rates, alongside increased use of chemical fertilisers. The expanded land use tied to greater production was flagged as a critical environmental risk due to its potential to exacerbate biodiversity loss and degrade ecosystems. Additionally, the use of AI-based innovations could also generate environmental spillovers. These findings led to a key policy recommendation: FLW reduction must go hand in hand with investments in sustainable agricultural practices to avoid adverse environmental impacts.

Additionally, the Partial Equilibrium Model (which captures the effects of FLW reduction measures on a single commodity value chain) highlighted the cost-benefit trade-offs. Although FLW reduction offers environmental benefits, the strategies themselves often come with high implementation costs. Therefore, a core recommendation was the need to reduce abatement costs to ensure the economic viability of FLW policies and improve their adoption across the food system.

Complementing these modelling insights, the ZeroW Policy Team identified a 'Just Transition Pathway'. Grounded in an extensive literature review, the 'Just Transition Pathway' offers a forward-looking vision of more resilient and equitable food systems. At the core of this definition stand the needs of the most vulnerable actors in the food system (both consumers and supply chain actors). From this perspective, SFSCs not only help cut FLW but also empower actors who are weaker in the conventional long supply chain, including producers and less affluent consumers. A just transition must therefore ensure that innovation benefits all participants in the food system, regardless of scale or location. However, transitioning towards a SFSC system comes with scaling challenges such as limited production capacity, logistical difficulties, and competition with mass-market products. In response, the project called for public investment in logistics infrastructure, digital platforms, and last-mile delivery solutions.

Furthermore, the literature review emphasised the importance of equity considerations: economic barriers may prevent small-scale actors from participating in SFSCs, making targeted support essential. FLW monitoring also emerged as a priority to support systemic change. Key actions should include mandatory waste data disclosure, investment in digital infrastructure, standardised measurement tools, and incentive structures to catalyse reduction initiatives. From a policy implementation perspective, the project outlined concrete actions for a just transition. These included strengthening the resilience of primary producers through financial and technical support, the adoption of sustainable practices, and ensuring access to innovative solutions, particularly for vulnerable actors. The project also underscored the importance of collaborative investment models (e.g., shared machinery) and peer-to-peer knowledge exchange to disseminate innovations across diverse agricultural contexts.

In parallel, the project highlighted the potential and challenges of scaling waste reduction technologies in the Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs).

- SILL1 demonstrated how a data platform tracking FLW across the supply chain can improve decision-making. However, building such a platform raised challenges around business model viability, governance, and semantic interoperability (addressed through the "semantic treehouse" tool).
- SILL3, focused on greenhouse tomato production, tackled pre-harvest and harvest losses due to mismatched supply and demand. It tested AI-based tools for yield and quality forecasting and harvest timing. However, uptake was hindered by farmers' reluctance, lack of data-sharing agreements, and the complexity of setting up marketplaces for excess produce, which ultimately had to be deprioritised.
- SILL4, focused on deploying a mobile food processing unit - a compact, on-wheels hub capable of turning perishable surplus into value-added products, which was tested and validated in real-life scenarios, confirming it is highly suitable for short supply chains and regional actors. The pilot demonstrated how mobility and adaptability enable regional stakeholders to process food on-site, reducing waste and strengthening local food systems.
- SILL5 piloted AI systems to classify cherry tomatoes according to quality (Brix and firmness) and cosmetic imperfections, with the aim of adding value to food that would otherwise be lost. The developed models are effective but require a large number of samples for each calibration.
- SILL6 addressed inefficiencies in quality control, currently a manual and periodic process prone to food losses. By developing real-time, digital tools for process optimisation, the project showed potential to reduce losses proactively. Yet again, challenges around operator acceptance and data-sharing for algorithm training were central.

In sum, the project offered a multi-level understanding of the food chain's structural issues, ranging from environmental trade-offs and economic feasibility to technological adoption and social equity. This evidence base informed a comprehensive set of policy recommendations for reducing FLW while ensuring a just and sustainable transition across the agri-food system. In the following paragraph, a set of key policy recommendations combining the evidence from the project is provided, aiming to guide policymakers in promoting a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system. Particular emphasis will be put on the importance of SFSCs. They are commonly organised through Alternative Food Networks (AFNs), such as community-supported agriculture (CSAs), farmers' markets, solidarity purchasing groups, and food cooperatives. These forms of food governance are crucial in fostering more resilient, inclusive, and sustainable agri-food systems.

Key Policy Recommendations

1. Strengthen SFSCs for resilient primary production

Building on the ZeroW project's findings, particularly from WP1 and WP8, support for SFSCs and AFNs emerges as essential for several interconnected reasons. First, SFSCs can significantly reduce FLW by minimising distribution distances and the number of intermediaries (Voge et al., 2023). This leads to lower transport losses, better matching between local supply and demand, and reduced waste from unsold perishables. Second, SFSCs display enhanced resilience in the face of systemic shocks, such as pandemics, geopolitical tensions, and energy crises (Michel-Villarreal et al., 2021; Usca and Tisenkopfs, 2023). Third, SFSCs contribute to a just transition by promoting food sovereignty, democratic governance, local employment, and the inclusion of underrepresented actors. Fourth, SFSCs are shown to strengthen local economies. Empirical evidence, including cases from France and China referenced in the project, illustrates that they generate more jobs per hectare and offer more stable employment compared to long, industrialised food supply chains.

Crucially, the project underscored the need for FLW reduction strategies that do not exacerbate environmental spillovers through intensified agricultural production. SFSCs, by tying production to local consumption and reinforcing community-level guarantees, offer a safeguard against unsustainable intensification. They thus align with the project's recommendation to combine FLW policies with sustainable primary production. This approach also addresses the modelling results, which warn of trade-offs, such as increased emissions or biodiversity loss, if FLW reduction measures are implemented without systemic reform.

In light of these findings, supporting SFSCs and AFNs is not only about reducing waste but also about reshaping the food system to be more resilient and sustainable. Their focus on sustainable primary production, their embeddedness in

local communities, and their capacity to buffer systemic risks make them key instruments for achieving the ZeroW project's vision of a just, near-zero FLW transition.

Examples of policy actions under Recommendation 1:

- Provide grants, public credit, or loan guarantees to support the start-up and scaling of SFSC initiatives, leveraging EU funds such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and Rural Development Policy (Joint Research Centre, 2013).
- Apply tax exemptions or incentives for local producers (e.g. France's tax breaks, Italy's "Zero Kilometer" law), and stabilise incomes within SFSCs considering part-time, seasonal, and family labour (Nagy, 2025; Strenght2Food, 2021).
- Promote green public procurement prioritising local and organic food in institutions (e.g., schools, hospitals) and set clear municipal targets or quotas for local sourcing (e.g., Florence's 70% requirement, UK's "30:30" campaign).
- Enable large-scale public-private investments in SFSC innovation, particularly in logistics and digitalisation, and use public funds to correct market failures and ensure inclusive access to infrastructure.
- Ensure fair and competitive pricing for SFSC products, promoting cost parity with long supply chains by reducing externalities (e.g., carbon pricing) and internalising social/environmental benefits.
- Develop a legal definition of Alternative Food Networks at the EU level and introduce municipal or supra-municipal carbon taxes or incentives supporting zero-kilometer production.
- Conduct feasibility studies and strategic diagnostics to assess local readiness for SFSCs, including logistics capacity, agricultural base, and economic niches.
- Provide access to, or rental of, public infrastructure (e.g., logistics centers, cold storage, food processing facilities) for SFSC actors.
- Strengthen producer cooperatives and clusters to ensure quality, supply consistency, and shared logistics and storage systems.
- Foster training, peer-learning, and knowledge-sharing platforms among producers, logistics actors, and consumers, including EU-supported "beacon" SFSC initiatives.
- Facilitate access for small-scale, young, and women farmers by offering land, training, and tailored support, including agricultural incubators and pilot areas for sustainable local production.
- Promote public enterprises in primary production services (e.g., food processing, waste and forest management) to lower entry barriers and enhance inclusion.

2. Enhance agricultural sustainability through innovation and digital data access

Digitalisation and sustainability are frequently referred to as the "twin transitions" shaping the future of the European food system. Although they stem from different origins and pursue distinct objectives, their interaction can be mutually beneficial, particularly in addressing FLW. By enabling data-driven decision-making throughout the food chain, from production to consumption, digital tools can help optimise logistics, anticipate surplus, and enhance redistribution strategies.

The ZeroW project offers a compelling example of how digital technologies, especially those supporting interoperable data exchange, can address structural barriers to reducing FLW and support more sustainable outcomes. Yet, realising the full potential of digital innovation for a fair and inclusive transition requires engaging with a series of systemic challenges. The dominant food chain, due to its scale and complexity, often grapples with entrenched data silos, limited transparency, and a resistance to infrastructural change. At the same time, while SFSCs demonstrate greater flexibility and local responsiveness, they frequently encounter obstacles such as constrained access to digital tools, capital, and logistics infrastructure. Furthermore, there is the need to address cultural concerns by acknowledging farmers' fear of losing their artisan identity and communicating the practical and environmental benefits of digitalisation, especially regarding FLW reduction, as suggested by the implementation of the ZeroW SILLs.

Examples of policy actions under Recommendation 2:

- Establish a European "Data Space" for FLW to enable secure, interoperable data sharing across actors, supported by incentives like regulatory credits, tax breaks, and pilot public-private partnerships for real-time inventory tracking. This is particularly relevant for monitoring FLW and guiding the value chain transition. A crucial lesson learned in SILL1 was that demonstrating immediate benefits (like improved client relationships or compliance) is key to securing data contributions from farmers and service providers.
- Ensure equitable access to digital infrastructure by addressing barriers such as poor broadband, low digital literacy, and high costs in rural or geopolitically vulnerable regions; tailor funding schemes (e.g., CAP, rural development funds) to local needs and avoid a one-size-fits-all approach.
- Promote the co-development of digital tools with farmers to ensure they are context-specific, compatible with existing practices, and scalable across diverse farm types and locations. Use public funding (e.g., CAP) to support participatory codesign processes and compensate farmers for their contributions to tool development and testing

- Improve transparency and accessibility of financial instruments for digitalisation (e.g., grants, subsidies, tax reliefs), especially for small farms and underrepresented groups.
- Incentivise digital solution providers to offer free trials, flexible pricing, and customised solutions that address different user profiles and farm structures.
- Design inclusive policy measures that explicitly integrate gender, recognising, for example, the roles of women in managing smaller, sustainable farms and favouring peer-led knowledge sharing.
- Align regulations and policy timelines with the digital innovation lifecycle and Return on Investment (ROI) to prevent conflicts and support adoption.
- Promote digitalisation as a pathway to encourage farm succession and attract younger generations to farming.
- Invest in diverse, inclusive, and adaptive training formats that blend technical and soft skills, co-designed with users (e.g., women managing farm administration), and offer both live and digital learning tailored to SMEs and farmers of all ages.
- Support peer-to-peer learning by integrating activities like farm visits into CAP-funded knowledge-sharing schemes.
- Provide significant public and private investments to enable digital innovation in SFSCs, particularly where market incentives fall short.

3. Support sustainability transitions in the food chain with interventions targeting logistics and transportation

Sustainable logistics and transportation are essential components of a just transition towards zero FLW, as highlighted throughout the ZeroW project. By enabling efficient, low carbon, and inclusive systems for the redistribution or valorisation of surplus food, logistics play a key role in reducing waste across the agri-food chain. However, insights from ZeroW's modelling work stress that FLW reduction strategies must be carefully designed to avoid negative environmental and socio-economic spillovers, such as increased emissions from intensified agricultural production. To mitigate these risks, logistics interventions should be accompanied by support for sustainable agricultural practices and equitable economic models.

Moreover, findings from the 'Just Transition Pathway' and the Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) underscore the importance of strengthening SFSCs through targeted investments in infrastructure, digital platforms, and last-mile delivery. These investments not only enhance climate resilience and reduce urban congestion but also empower vulnerable actors across the supply chain. Ultimately, building a resilient logistics ecosystem is not merely a technical fix but a structural lever for driving systemic change in how food is produced, distributed, and valued.

Examples of policy actions under Recommendation 3:

- Enable reverse logistics by redirecting unsold or surplus food to producers, food banks, composting facilities, or bioconversion plants. This can be enhanced by FLW monitoring systems coordinated at local/regional level and digital tools to track inefficiencies and optimise recovery routes.
- Establish local/regional urban agri-food logistics hubs that integrate SFSC logistics and reduce long-distance freight traffic. Enable flexible use of underutilised public spaces (e.g., warehouses, market halls) for these hubs, especially in dense cities.
- Accelerate the energy transition in local food logistics by subsidising feasibility studies for biogas or e-fuel production from FLW (including co-digestion with manure) and for agrivoltaics systems powering logistics.
- Provide targeted subsidies and leasing incentives for electric vans, cargo bikes, shared EVs, and EV charging infrastructure in rural and peri-urban areas.
- Fund and incubate cooperative logistics models such as food co-ops and cooperative delivery systems using cargo bikes or small EVs. Provide legal, technical, and financial support for AFNs, smallholders, and low-income actors to invest in logistics infrastructure, EVs, and digital tools.
- Facilitate structured dialogue among AFNs, retailers, and logistics providers to co-invest in infrastructure and overcome coordination barriers. Support regional roundtables with public facilitation and create public agencies or observatories to map flows, identify inefficiencies, coordinate infrastructure, and implement territorial food strategies.
- Shift long-distance transport of agri-food products to rail and intermodal solutions by promoting initiatives that move long-distance transport of preserved, bulk, or packaged foods from road to rail. Prioritise intermodal terminals, refrigerated containers, EV-based first/last-mile delivery, and flexible rail services like night trains or modular carriages suited to food logistics.
- Promote low-impact and zero-emission last-mile distribution by encouraging consumer adoption of sustainable last mile options through incentives (e.g., discounts for bike pickup) and ensuring food hubs are accessible via bike paths and public transport, integrating them into urban mobility plans.
- Fund vocational training in low-carbon logistics, fleet management, EV maintenance, cooperative governance, digital supply chains, and FLW prevention. Target support especially to young farmers, small producers, and logistics cooperatives.

- Develop certification and reporting standards for sustainable logistics and embed them in existing EU mechanisms such as the Farm to Fork Strategy and CAP monitoring systems.
- Mandate climate risk assessments for logistics investments, considering hazards like floods and heatwaves. Support resilient infrastructure through passive cooling, insulated storage, and off-grid energy systems in rural and peri urban logistics hubs.

Conclusion

The ZeroW project clearly demonstrates that reducing FLW requires a systemic transformation of the food supply chain structure, emphasising shorter, more resilient, and inclusive food networks. Strengthening SFSCs not only curbs waste but also promotes environmental sustainability, social equity, and economic resilience by empowering vulnerable actors and fostering local economies. Simultaneously, harnessing digital innovation and ensuring equitable access to data and technology are essential to overcoming structural barriers and enhancing sustainability throughout the food system.

For a just transition aligned with the European Green Deal, the Farm to Fork goals and the newly adopted binding food waste reduction targets, policy must move beyond end-of-chain interventions and address the root structural challenges. This involves public investments in logistics, infrastructure, capacity-building, and tailored support for small-scale producers, alongside robust monitoring and transparent data-sharing frameworks. By combining sustainable agricultural practices with digital and organisational innovations, the EU can foster a fairer, greener, and more efficient food system that benefits producers, consumers, and the environment alike.

POLICY BRIEF: PARTICIPATORY LOCAL GOVERNANCE AND EMPOWERMENT FOR JUST ZERO FOOD WASTE TRANSITION WITHIN THE URBAN CONTEXT

Introduction

In the context of the European Union's recently approved binding national food waste reduction targets and the broader objectives of the Green Deal, actors beyond the formal food supply chain, such as local governments, municipalities, and non-governmental organisations (NGOs), hold an increasingly critical role in advancing a just transition toward sustainable food systems. By 2050, 70% of the global population is expected to live in urban areas, making cities central to both the challenges and solutions of sustainable food systems (United Nations, 2018).

In Europe, where 54% of food waste was generated at the household level in 2022, urban areas hold particular significance (Eurostat, 2024). While they may sit

outside the traditional food supply chain, cities wield considerable influence through public procurement, education, infrastructure, and community-level interventions. However, the complex and structural nature of food systems requires coordinated action among a diverse set of stakeholders, both food supply chain (FSC) and non-FSC actors - policymakers, food banks, cooperatives.

To align with the EU's goals of fostering inclusive, resilient, and regionally tailored food policies, it is imperative that policymakers actively engage these local actors through participatory governance and leverage their unique capacities to shape locally grounded, effective interventions that may significantly help reduce food waste. This policy brief recommends actions to strengthen the role of local and regional governments in reducing FLW. It is intended for EU policymakers seeking to support decentralised, effective, and inclusive FLW strategies. It follows the EU's Just Transition Pathway defined in the ZeroW project and will guide the action plans of Member States for the newly adopted binding targets.

Policy Problem

Urban food loss and waste policies are currently undermined by fragmented governance, weak institutional capacity, and persistent power imbalances that exclude smaller actors and vulnerable groups from participation. Municipalities often lack the mandate or tools to connect actors across the food system, yet they are uniquely positioned to bridge these gaps. At the same time, many innovations overlook behavioural and equity dimensions, offering few actionable pathways for urban actors to engage. Bureaucratic and administrative barriers further reinforce their exclusion, making it difficult to scale effective interventions or ensure fair access to support mechanisms. Crucially, the implementation of several Just Pathway Actions identified within ZeroW, particularly Actions 2, 4, 5, and 7, is highly dependent on urban environments and governance structures (see Figure 4). These include improving food waste monitoring (Action 2), subsidising FLW-reducing technologies (Action 4), enabling behavioural change through targeted consumer incentives (Action 5), and most importantly strengthening collaboration with external actors like NGOs (Action 7). Cities are central to these actions due to their capacity to coordinate across sectors, their infrastructure, and proximity to consumers.

However, implementation at the urban level faces challenges such as:

- Limited municipal authority over fiscal levers (e.g., tax incentives or procurement standards);
- Fragmented or siloed governance, with unclear leadership on food-related responsibilities
- Poor data availability and inadequate funding to support innovation uptake;
- Underutilised synergies between urban food strategies and national ones.

Addressing these issues requires aligning urban food policy with broader 'Just Transition Pathway' strategies and unlocking cities' potential as key implementation arenas.

Evidence from Project

Urban areas are central in the food system and hotspots of FLW. Evidence from the ZeroW project emphasises that reducing FLW in cities requires not just technological innovation, but coordinated, cross-sectoral action and enabling governance environments. Key lessons from the project's innovations and Just Pathway Actions demonstrate the importance of collaborative mechanisms and data-driven infrastructure in urban contexts.

The project findings explicitly emphasise the importance of integrating external actors into FLW governance, formally recognising cities and NGOs as core contributors to the development and implementation of the just pathway. Effective collaboration is crucial; cities, NGOs, cooperatives, and food banks must actively collaborate and a relevant tool to create systemic solutions include Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs).

To facilitate meaningful participation, institutional support and dedicated funding mechanisms are required, particularly to ensure inclusive partnerships involving smaller actors and vulnerable communities. Policy frameworks should therefore prioritise collaborative governance, embedding cities and local governments within national and EU-level planning processes through participatory mechanisms. Moreover, equity and justice principles, aligned with the 'Just Transition Pathway', must underpin local implementation strategies, safeguarding against regulatory measures disproportionately impacting vulnerable groups such as small-scale farmers and minority communities. Finally, ZeroW's stakeholders consistently highlight the necessity of prioritising preventive approaches, advocating strongly for measures that tackle waste at its source rather than relying predominantly on downstream waste treatment options.

SILL4 (fruit & vegetable redistribution) capacity building activities in Barcelona highlight how enabling governance structures and aligned political responsibilities can significantly improve food redistribution outcomes. There, a single government department oversees both food waste and food aid, allowing streamlined policy and implementation. Fiscal incentives (like VAT exemptions and corporate tax deductions) and legal obligations have made redistribution a viable and attractive pathway for producers and retailers. These measures are supported by an integrated food redistribution network, simplifying logistics and collaboration with Producer Organisations (POs). In contrast, fragmented governance in regions like Belgium creates duplication, inefficiencies, and underutilised infrastructure, despite strong local initiatives. This suggests that urban FLW policy must prioritise

institutional coordination, simplification of processes, and long-term investment in food aid infrastructure.

Cross-cutting insights also emerge from pathway actions, such as efforts to build local ecosystems for food waste valorisation. These reveal that while innovation pilots are often technically viable, scaling them requires coordinated action across municipal services, civil society, logistics providers, and local businesses. Quick wins, such as improving redistribution through better storage, transport, and digital platforms, often stall due to unclear roles, missing governance, or lack of structural funding. As such, mapping actors, clarifying responsibilities, and setting up shared governance mechanisms are essential steps for municipalities looking to reduce urban FLW.

Data availability and standardisation are consistent barriers. Across SILLs, data sharing is constrained by unclear ownership, lack of incentives, and limited interoperability. Successful initiatives (e.g., SILL1's semantic data approach) show that progress depends on building communities of practice, not only technical standards. Urban FLW policy should therefore support the development of shared data spaces, aligned with EU data strategies, and invest in capacity-building to help local actors engage with them meaningfully.

Alignment of Just Pathway Actions with existing Urban Policy Instruments:

The Just Pathway Actions identified in ZeroW align with several existing urban policy instruments and initiatives, creating important synergies that can accelerate implementation (see Figure 4):

- Just Pathway Action 4: Subsidised waste reduction technologies → Matches innovation procurement and green public purchasing frameworks already used by several cities (e.g., in school food services or waste management contracts). Municipalities can apply these to scale digital redistribution platforms or logistics innovations.
- Just Pathway Action 5: Targeted consumer incentives → Builds on urban tools for public engagement, nudging, and education (e.g., campaigns, citizen science, or reward schemes for waste separation). Synergies exist with local health and sustainability education programs
- Just Pathway Action 7: Inclusion of external actors and collaboration → Leverages local food policy councils, city networks, and multi-actor governance models. Local governments possess a wide range of action levers to address food waste - spanning urban planning, public procurement, taxation, regulation, municipal food services, public engagement, and waste management.

These synergies suggest that many cities already have the institutional entry points to operationalise the 'Just Transition Pathway', but need additional support,

mandate, and coordination to scale impact and ensure equitable participation. Hence, these findings guide the following policy recommendations.

Key Policy Recommendations

Local and regional governments are crucial enablers of food system transformation. They possess a wide range of action levers to address food waste - spanning urban planning, public procurement, taxation, regulation, municipal food services, public engagement, and waste management (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2). Their proximity to local food system actors - producers, distributors and consumers - also positions them uniquely to lead cross sector collaboration, influence behavioural change, and engage diverse stakeholders. In doing so, local governments can help address power imbalances and foster inclusive governance in line with the Green Deal and the Farm to Fork Strategy.

Given their strategic role, local and regional governments are well-positioned to implement the following target actions to reduce FLW and foster more sustainable and equitable food systems:

- Promote and coordinate agri-food logistics hubs to enhance supply chain and reduce waste. These hubs serve as critical infrastructure within regional food systems and can significantly mitigate FLW through better coordination among stakeholders (the Emilia-Romagna Mercati – Rete di Imprese is a best practice in this sense) (Emilia-Romagna Mercati, 2025).
- Facilitate cross-sector partnerships between logistics hubs, producers' organizations, food banks, and charity associations to redirect surplus food and prevent waste. The Parma CAL within the Logistica Solidale project is an effective example of collaboration orchestrated by local authorities to achieve measurable reductions in FLW (ParmaCAL, 2025).
- Leverage existing relationships with producers' organizations, particularly through Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) implementation, to support the development of public-private data-sharing communities focused on FLW. Regional administrations can play a central role in creating interoperable data ecosystems using a data space approach, enabling evidence-based decision-making and greater transparency across the value chain.
- Support Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs), such as farmers' markets and alternative food networks, which contribute to FLW reduction by connecting producers more directly with consumers. Local governments can map existing SFSCs, identify their needs, and provide targeted support through capacity-building initiatives, and by facilitating access to shared physical and digital infrastructure.

To ensure implementation, urban policy actors must institutionalise multi-actor governance structures (e.g., Food Policy Councils [i], like the Ernährungsrat Freiburg

& Region, and the Cork Food Policy Council) that align and coordinate efforts across planning, procurement, and waste services and help embed FLW goals into local climate and food strategies (Den Boer, 2023; Ernährungsrat Freiburg, 2025; Cork Healthy Cities, 2025).

To translate broad EU goals into municipal action, cities should adopt measurable, context-specific targets through local food strategies. Embedding EU-aligned FLW objectives into municipal performance frameworks enables accountability, continuity, and comparability across urban contexts. Participating in transnational networks such as the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact also facilitates benchmarking, peer learning, and funding access (Milan Urban Food Policy Pact, 2025). However, municipalities often lack the authority to fully implement legal, fiscal, or systemic interventions. EU and national policymakers must create an enabling environment to scale urban innovations and align them with systemic change.

1. Strengthen multi-level governance to enable systemic, evidence-informed action on urban food waste

Establish formal cooperation mechanisms across national, regional, and local levels to support the integration of food waste reduction into urban planning and local food strategies. Effective multi-level governance is essential to building sustainable food systems and must be guided by evidence-informed frameworks that reflect the complexity of food systems, the diversity of stakeholders involved, and the trade-offs inherent in policy decisions (Circle Economy, 2020). Initiatives such as the FutureFoodS Partnership and FOODPathS project show how cross-sectoral and cross-level collaboration can accelerate systemic change (FutureFoodS Partnership, 2025; FOODPathS, 2025).

2. Promote multi-actor collaboration for urban food waste reduction

Encourage the development of local Food Waste Alliances that bring together governments, retailers, platforms, and NGOs to co-design context-specific solutions to food waste. Models like the RÉGAL network¹³ in France, and the Food Waste Free United in the Netherlands¹⁴ show how collaborative action can yield tangible results (Ministère de l'Agriculture et de l'Alimentation, 2025; Samen Tegen Voedselverspilling, 2025). To scale these approaches, EU support is needed for peer learning platforms, digital infrastructure, and inclusive innovation practices that engage smaller actors, build trust, and ensure equitable participation in waste-reduction initiatives.

3. Incentivise the adoption of national and regional sustainable procurement standards to align cities' public spending with food waste reduction goals

Adopt EU-wide sustainable procurement standards that prioritise food waste prevention in public catering services. By shifting away from purely cost-based criteria, procurement can drive suppliers to adopt waste-reducing practices, such as surplus redistribution and menu optimisation. The Buy Better Food Manifesto for Establishing Minimum Standards for Public Canteens Across the EU and innovative school food procurement models from the SchoolFood4Change project are examples of practical guidance (EU Food Policy Coalition, 2022; SchoolFood4Change, 2025). Malmö's school meal system, for instance, integrates food waste and sustainability criteria into contracts while improving access to healthy meals.

4. Revise tax frameworks at national or regional level to encourage food redistribution and discourage food waste

Use fiscal policy to influence food supply chain behaviour by aligning tax incentives with food waste prevention objectives. Tax breaks can reward surplus food donations, while penalties or redirected levies can discourage landfill use. For example, France offers a 60% tax credit on donated food products, transferable over five years, while Catalonia redistributes landfill/incineration tax revenue to reward municipalities achieving better waste outcomes (European Commission, 2019; Interreg Europe, 2024). These models offer replicable strategies for fostering sustainable behaviour through taxation.

5. Foster the adoption of monitoring tools focusing not only on waste volume but also on participation equity and systemic impact

Develop urban FLW monitoring frameworks that capture both quantitative and qualitative dimensions - tracking not only waste volumes, but also participation equity and governance performance. Indicators should assess how inclusive waste reduction programs are (e.g., participation of SMEs and minority-led initiatives), and whether governance is coherent and accountable. The SILL4 capacity building activity in Barcelona highlights the need for role clarity and coordination. Monitoring tools such as dashboards, transparency indicators, and longitudinal policy tracking can illuminate progress, gaps, and opportunities for institutional reform [ii].

Conclusion Local and regional governments play a crucial role in reducing food waste and advancing sustainable food systems. The recommendations outlined ranging from promoting cross-sector partnerships to revising fiscal policies, highlight the urgent need for EU policymakers to support local actors in their efforts to reduce food waste, while aligning with broader EU objectives such as the Green Deal and the Farm to Fork strategy. These actions are not only feasible but necessary to ensure that food waste reduction initiatives are effectively tailored to local contexts, empower vulnerable communities, and drive meaningful change across Europe. With coordinated efforts, robust policy frameworks, and the active

engagement of local governments, the EU can achieve its food waste reduction targets and foster the development of more resilient, sustainable food systems.

POLICY BRIEF: EFFECTIVE GOVERNANCE FOR A JUST ZERO FOOD WASTE TRANSITION

Introduction

Food Loss and Waste (FLW) challenge the sustainability and fairness of the EU food system, affecting environmental goals and economic resilience. Addressing FLW requires coordinated governance that balances incentives, accountability, and collaboration across diverse food system actors. This policy brief presents evidence-based recommendations to support inclusive, transparent, and effective governance frameworks aligned with the EU's Just Transition, which will guide the action plans of Member States for the newly adopted binding food waste reduction targets.

Policy Problem

FLW amounts remain high due to the lack of a coherent governance framework that ensures transparency, accountability, and coordinated action across the food supply chain. Companies are not consistently required to measure or report FLW, and current policies offer limited incentives for prevention, data sharing, or collaboration. To meet the current EU food waste reduction targets in the context of a Just Transition, urgent action is needed to establish governance that mandates transparent reporting, rewards effective waste reduction, and supports inclusive, co-created solutions across the food supply chain (FSC).

Evidence from Project

ZeroW project findings highlight that a non-punitive, incentive-based governance approach is both effective and widely supported across the food supply chain (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2). Roundtable discussions with FSC stakeholders emphasised that positive incentives, such as tax reductions or waivers for verified food waste reduction practices like redistribution, can drive voluntary corporate action, provided they are underpinned by mandatory FLW tracking to ensure transparency and fairness (Mesiranta, Närvänen, Mattila, 2022). Additionally, a tiered FLW taxation system, adjusted according to business size, income level, or waste volume, was identified as a promising policy tool to ensure proportionate enforcement, while supporting equity across actors in the food system.

This progressive approach, as highlighted in the OECD's 2025 review of global FLW policy environments, can help tailor incentives and enforcement to different food system stages (OECD, 2025). Evidence from the project further reinforces the importance of horizontal peer-learning and data-sharing mechanisms, as

demonstrated in its SILL7's food bank network where trust and collaboration were strengthened through inclusive and transparent practices. Similarly, SILL1's focus on developing a data hub strategy and semantic interoperability revealed critical barriers and enablers related to digital governance.

The pilots highlighted the importance of clear data ownership contracts, early adopter engagement, and building trust through accessible tools and fast-feedback applications. These insights underline the need for policy frameworks that support interoperable data infrastructure, address governance and trust concerns, and promote community-building around data sharing, all of which are essential to realising digitalisation's full potential for FLW reduction. These findings confirm that embedding accountability in public procurement and financial support mechanisms, through performance-based contracts, third-party verification, and tailored Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) support, can accelerate FLW reduction while advancing a Just Transition that is inclusive, collaborative, and sustainable. Hence, these findings guide the following policy recommendations.

Key Policy Recommendations

1. Establish a non-punitive, incentive-based approach to food waste governance

A non-punitive, incentive-based approach to food waste governance focuses on encouraging positive change rather than relying solely on penalties. Such strategies include promoting sustainable consumption, supporting eco-innovation, incentivising food donations, and raising awareness among producers, retailers, and consumers. By stimulating voluntary action, collaboration, and continuous improvement, these approaches foster a culture of responsibility and innovation across the food system.

An example of this balanced model is Spain's Law 1/2025 on the Prevention of Food Loss and Waste, which combines incentives with targeted enforcement (Boletín Oficial del Estado, 2025). The law encourages the sale of "imperfect" but edible produce, requires food waste prevention plans, prioritises food donations, and mandates that restaurants provide free takeaway containers for leftovers. These non-punitive measures are designed to motivate all actors to reduce waste, while enforcement mechanisms ensure compliance when necessary. This integrated approach demonstrates how incentives and proportionate regulation can work together to accelerate progress toward national and EU food waste reduction goals.

Governments and public agencies play a crucial role in shaping market behaviour through procurement choices and financial support mechanisms. By linking corporate accountability for FLW to eligibility for public funding, subsidies,

and procurement contracts, policymakers can create strong incentives for companies to prioritise sustainable practices.

Accountability in public procurement related to food waste reduction can be controversial due to concerns about increased administrative burdens and fairness. To address this, performance-based incentives offer a balanced solution by rewarding measurable achievements rather than imposing penalties alone. Examples include financial rewards, tax benefits, public recognition, and preferential contracting for suppliers who meet or exceed food waste reduction targets. This approach encourages innovation and collaboration, making accountability more acceptable and effective across the supply chain.

To operationalise this approach, companies applying for public contracts, grants, or subsidies should be required to demonstrate transparent and standardised reporting on their FLW. Reporting should align with internationally recognised frameworks, such as the FLW Standard by WRI or FAO guidelines, and be tailored to the size and operational scope of each company (WRI, 2016; FAO, 2016). This includes mandatory disclosure of waste reduction targets and measurable progress. Such a requirement would create a level playing field, ensuring that all applicants are held to consistent standards while encouraging meaningful efforts to reduce waste. It would also enhance public trust by ensuring that taxpayer-funded initiatives support sustainability goals and provide governments with reliable data to track progress towards national and international targets, including SDG 12.3 and therefore guiding the action plans of Member States for the newly adopted binding targets.

To support this shift toward performance-based accountability, a range of governance innovations and practical tools should be introduced. Performance-based contracts can link continued funding or contract renewals to FLW reduction benchmarks, while procurement scoring systems and bonus incentives can reward bidders with strong track records or ambitious targets. Effective enforcement requires regular audits and independent verification to ensure data accuracy, with proportionate penalties such as funding clawbacks or disqualification from future bids in cases of non-compliance. Oversight could be led by an independent body or existing public institutions, supported by third-party verifiers to maintain credibility. At the same time, tailored support for SMEs is critical to ensure inclusive participation.

As emphasised in ZeroW's SILL2 and the Just Pathway Action 4, this includes training programs, technical assistance, financial support for tracking technologies, simplified reporting templates, and phased implementation timelines (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2; see Figure 4). Innovation prizes and cost sharing for certification can further encourage SMEs to engage in waste reduction efforts, ensuring that

accountability measures are both ambitious and achievable across all business sizes.

2. Increase accountability and transparency in digitalisation and public procurement

Digitalisation and sustainability are regarded as a “twin transition” in Europe: albeit having different starting points and goals, they can profoundly support each other, e.g. via digital solutions that can make sustainable decision-making easier, increasing digital skills in return. However, the adoption of digital solutions for sustainability in the food chain is not a binary yes/no decision. It is a journey comprised of different phases, from awareness to consideration and implementation. Inherently linked to increased digitalisation is the reliance on data, motivating all sorts of questions and insecurities around data governance that arise during this adoption journey. Policymakers can help make the journey smoother and more secure by implementing assurances around data governance and data ownership.

Policymakers can do this through the following approaches:

- Policymakers can communicate data governance policies, such as the EU Data Act (2024) and the EU code of conduct on agricultural data sharing by contractual agreement (2018) and ensure these are accessible to all intended audiences and can be well interpreted by them (European Union, 2023; FEFAC, 2018).
- Additionally, regulatory frameworks for the technology sector can help to ensure that owners and generators of data remain in control of their data.

Several uncertainties surrounding digitalisation require careful consideration from policymakers:

- **Accountability:** Clarify responsibilities regarding unintended outcomes from digital technologies, such as robotics, and address implications for existing labour agreements. Ongoing policy development should aim to manage such uncertainties clearly and effectively.
- **Preservation of traditional knowledge:** While promoting digital solutions to reduce FLW, policymakers should simultaneously encourage the documentation and retention of traditional knowledge, intuition, and practical experimentation. Balancing innovation with established practices ensures resilience and continued adaptation.
- **Building trust:** Effective policy implementation depends heavily on public trust. Trust levels vary based on historical and socio-cultural contexts; for example, communities in post-communist societies or rural areas distant from urban centres may exhibit lower trust in governmental initiatives. Policymakers must consistently demonstrate transparency and reliability

through coherent communication and inclusive policies, particularly targeting enhanced engagement with rural farming communities.

3. Create EU-level guidelines for co-governance of Just Transition in the food system

The EU should develop concrete guidelines for co-governance that enable shared decision-making between public authorities and food system actors. Evidence from ZeroW's stakeholder consultations and pathway simulations confirms that top-down enforcement or purely market-driven measures, such as flat-rate food waste taxes or voluntary innovation alone, often fail to address structural disparities and can lead to unintended spillovers, such as waste shifting across supply chain stages or penalising vulnerable groups like small farmers and informal retailers.

EU-level co-governance guidelines should promote inclusive collaboration between governments, farmers, processors, retailers, NGOs, and consumers, ensuring that FLW reduction targets are context-sensitive and co-developed. Local engagement is essential to tailor policy instruments, such as differentiated taxation, incentive schemes, and digital solutions, to the real operational capacities of different actors. Simulations from the MAGNET model show that FLW policies can produce both environmental gains and economic distortions, underscoring the need for more adaptive and collaborative governance frameworks (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2).

Drawing from ZeroW systemic lens, such guidelines should promote differentiated targets by sector, commodity, and actor capacity, while embedding circular economy principles that prioritise prevention over disposal (ZeroW Deliverable 8.2). Public-private partnerships, community-level initiatives, and inclusive data-sharing standards, such as those piloted in ZeroW SILLs, demonstrate the feasibility of co-creating solutions that are both ambitious and implementable. The EU can lead by facilitating knowledge transfer, supporting governance innovation, and ensuring policy consistency across Member States, enabling a food system transformation that is fair, effective, and resilient.

Conclusion

Achieving a resilient, sustainable, and equitable food system within the EU requires coordinated policy actions on multiple fronts. Firstly, establishing a non-punitive, incentive-based framework for food waste governance will encourage proactive participation from all stakeholders, fostering innovation and collective responsibility. Secondly, increasing accountability and transparency in digitalisation and public procurement is essential to build trust, mitigate risks, and ensure technologies genuinely benefit agricultural communities. Finally, developing comprehensive EU-level guidelines for co-governance will enable inclusive decision-making processes, ensuring that the transition to sustainability is both just and

equitable. Together, these measures can underpin a robust and fair transformation of Europe's food system.

4. Intended use and dissemination of the ZeroW EU Policy Briefs

The ZeroW EU Policy Briefs are an exploitable outcome of the project, constituting a culmination of the WP8 work and approach. Taken together, they outline a guiding framework for EU (and national) policymakers to reach a fairer food system.

Firstly, the briefs should function as a **practical decision support tool**. As outlined in Chapter 2, they convert project evidence into clear recommendations and policy choices, highlighting the relevant trade-offs and implications. Together, they map the stepping stones toward a coherent policy framework that is essential for a just pathway to near-zero food loss and waste by 2050. The short- term and medium-term recommendations can be used to align priorities across ministries and sectors, provide a credible basis for capacity building, and strengthen commitment by incentivising action from all stakeholders. For example, by incentivising the adoption of national and regional sustainable procurement standards to align cities' public spending with food waste reduction goals. In this sense, the briefs also serve as an **agenda setting instrument** for policymakers, by highlighting priority issues and areas for intervention, diagnosing gaps in the current approach, and proposing actionable steps to address them.

Moreover, the briefs highlight the crucial need for improved cooperation across all stakeholders of the FSC and continued knowledge-sharing. This alone may allow for sustained progress if actively addressed and prioritised by policymakers, for instance by establishing formal cooperation mechanisms across national, regional, and local level as indicated in the Urban context brief. In diagnosing crucial gaps and providing recommendations, the briefs also provide **areas for further policy development and advocacy windows**. These include prioritising precise measurement in the context of the newly binding food waste reduction targets, with clear baselines and allocation of responsibilities across the FSC. As argued in several briefs, this must be backed by interoperable data arrangements that protect confidentiality and keep reporting proportionate. To achieve a truly just pathway, economic instruments need refinement to reward prevention and reuse while addressing distributional effects and disadvantages on households and smaller operators. The overall objective should be a coherent framework for waste reduction that is incentive-based, clarifying practices, providing appropriate liability safeguards, and streamlining compliance for smaller businesses. Public procurement can act as a strong lever in catering and food service through criteria that favour prevention and valorisation, while consumers should be actively

engaged through targeted interventions that position them as active participants in the just transition, using positive rather than punitive messaging. These priorities align with the concrete advocacy windows outlined in Chapter 2, including consultations on EU guidance and implementing or delegated acts for measurement and reporting, national budget and programme cycles for economic instruments, framework agreement renewals for procurement criteria, ongoing reviews of labelling rules and initiatives for consumer information and engagement, and municipal budget approvals. Positioning the briefs at these junctures can convert recommendations into impactful policy choices.

Following publication of the policy briefs in early September 2025, the ZeroW Policy team promptly identified **priority dissemination opportunities** and engaged with relevant events:

- As Policy Team Leader, SAFE published the policy briefs on its website and initiated dissemination through its communication channels, while WP8 partners supported outreach via their own networks, especially in the context of the International Day of Awareness of Food Loss and Waste on 29 September 2025.
- SAFE participated in the ReTaste International Conference in Athens, Greece on 24-27 September 2025, presenting the consumer- and food chain-focused policy briefs and engaging with several stakeholders from academia, industry, and civil society. The conference was a key opportunity to disseminate the policy briefs, network, and discuss the food waste reduction targets among other topics.
- The briefs were shared in the Food Working Group Action Plan of the Green Deal Support Office, strengthening cross-project collaboration. Additionally, SAFE co-wrote a joint policy brief with the projects SISTERS and TITAN, focusing on the scalability potential of the developed innovations, contributing key insights from ZeroW and the work undertaken in WP8.
- SAFE participated in the European Commission webinar with Food Loss and Waste projects, highlighting some challenges and opportunities from the policy briefs in the context of future R&I needs.
- SAFE will also disseminate the policy briefs at its Annual Conference 2025, *Advancing Consumer Protection through Research*, on 20 November 2025 in Brussels. This flagship event will convene policymakers, experts, stakeholders, and citizens from across Europe to discuss the future of food safety, food waste, and sustainability in the European Union, providing a strong platform for dissemination and engagement with the briefs.
- Additionally, the briefs will be shared in the EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub.

Dissemination efforts will continue beyond the end of WP8 in October 2025 and of ZeroW in December 2025. As mentioned earlier, the policy briefs constitute a foundational basis for critical agenda setting priorities toward near-zero FLW by 2050.

5. Conclusions

This report is the culmination of the work started in D8.1, drawing from the insights and analysis of D8.2 to produce five policy briefs that delve into crucial policy areas and present actionable short- and medium-term policy recommendations toward a near-zero FLW food system by 2050.

Building on D8.2, which conceptualised a just pathway and realistic intermediate food waste reduction targets through comprehensive analysis combining economic simulations and validation by external stakeholders, the ZeroW Policy team produced five EU Policy Briefs. These focus on four priority domains: actor specific policies for consumers and farmers; food chain structure with emphasis on short food supply chains; governance, setting out how food loss and waste reduction can be better integrated into frameworks and strategies; and context specific policies centred on the urban environment. These priorities underpin systemic change and align with the “Just Pathway Actions” identified in D8.2. Figure 5 provides an overview of the key recommendations presented in each EU Policy Brief:

Figure 5: Overview of the key policy recommendations

Ultimately, these policy recommendations should be seen as part of a broader coherent framework needed to bring about systemic change. Taken together, the policy briefs are a practical decision support tool for EU and national policymakers alike and may inform their agenda setting and priorities directly. Furthermore, the briefs point out areas for further policy development and advocacy windows, which policymakers should exploit to steer progress toward the just pathway. It is imperative to underline that real progress now depends on coordinated leadership, clear allocation of responsibilities, and the mobilisation of resources to implement the proposed actions across governance levels.

References

Bartelings, H. and Gatto, A. (2025) Analysis of the Impact of Zero Food Waste Scenarios: A MAGNET Analysis. Part II of Deliverable D1.3 of ZeroW Project.

Boletín Oficial del Estado (2025) *Ley de 5 de marzo de 2025, de la Agencia Española de Seguridad Alimentaria y Nutrición, por la que se publica el Convenio con la Asociación de Celíacos de Cataluña, sobre el apoyo al desarrollo del programa de actividades de información, formación y sensibilización a personas celiacas.* BOE. https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2025-6597

Campus Race to Zero Waste (2024) *Learn from Your Peers - Campus Race to Zero Waste.* Available at: [Learn From Your Peers - Campus Race To Zero Waste](#)

Circle Economy (2020) *The Urban Policy Instrument Framework –Using Policy to Steer Cities Toward a Circular Economy,* Circle Economy. Available at: <https://www.circle-economy.com/resources/the-urban-policy-framework>

Council of the European Union (2025) *Council and Parliament agree to reduce food waste and set new rules on waste textile.* Available at: [Council and Parliament agree to reduce food waste and set new rules on waste textile - Consilium](#)

Cork Healthy Cities (2025) *Cork Food Policy Council.* Available at: <https://corkhealthycities.com/cork-food-policy-council/>

Den Boer, A.C.L., Van der Valk, A.J.J., Regeer, B.J.&Broerse,J.E.W. (2023) *Food policy networks and their potential to stimulate systemic intermediation for food system transformation,* Local Environment, 28(10), 1201–1219.

Emilia-Romagna Mercati (2025) *Emilia-Romagna Mercati.* Available at: <https://emiliaromagnamercati.com/en/>

Ernährungsrat Freiburg (2025) *Ernährungsrat Freiburg.* Available at: <https://ernaehrungsrat-freiburg.de/>

European CAP Network (2025) *Assessing the impact of digital technology solutions in agriculture under real-life conditions,* European CAP Network. Available at: <https://eu->

cap-network.ec.europa.eu/projects/assessing-impact-digital-technology-solutions-agriculture-real-life-conditions_fr

European Commission (2025a) *Precision farming - EIP-AGRI*. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/digitising-agriculture/developing-digitaltechnologies/precision-farming-0.html>

European Commission (2025b) *Digitalisation of agriculture and rural areas in the EU*. Available at: [Digitalisation - European Commission](#)

European Commission (2025c) *CAP 2023-27*. Available at: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/cap-overview/cap-2023-27_en

European Commission (2025d) *A long-term vision for the EU's rural areas*. Available at: https://rural-vision.europa.eu/index_en

European Commission (2025e) *Supporting Smart Village strategies*. Available at: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/rural-development/supporting-smart-village-strategies_en

European Commission (2025f) *Common European data spaces for agriculture and mobility*. Available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/common-european-data-spaces-agriculture-and-mobility>

European Commission (2025g) *Summary record of the Sub-group on Consumer Food Waste Prevention, 20 May 2025*. Brussels: European Commission. Available at: https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/36930cef-469b-418a-8f62-1a98fdc75894_en

European Commission (2025h) *Summary record of the Sub-group on Action and Implementation, 10 April 2025*. Brussels: European Commission. Available at: https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/cd0e63be-48e7-4982-b0ee-8fbd6fee55f5_en

European Commission (2025i) *Summary record of the Sub-group on Food Loss and Waste Monitoring, 3 April 2025*. Brussels: European Commission. Available at:

https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/dd6c3829-c57b-4fc8-9754-0358d7691af2_en

European Commission (2025j) *Summary record of the Sub-group on Food Donation, 5 June 2025*. Brussels: European Commission. Available at: https://food.ec.europa.eu/document/download/ed629ce6-cab7-4fec-aaf0-b97b8baf7943_en

European Commission (2025k) *About the EU Platform*. Available at: [EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste - Food Safety](#)

European Commission (2024) *Digitalising the EU agricultural sector*. Available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/digitalisation-agriculture>

European Commission (2019) *Redistribution of surplus food: Examples of practices in the Member States*, EU Platform on Food Losses and Food Waste, Brussels. Available at : https://food.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-06/fw_eu-actions_food-donation_ms-practices-food-redis.pdf

EU Food Policy Coalition (2022) *Manifesto for establishing Minimum Standards for Public Canteens across the EU*, ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability. Available at: https://foodpolicycoalition.eu/wpcontent/uploads/2022/10/Manifesto-for-establishing-Minimum-Standards-for-PublicCanteens-across-the-EU_final.pdf

European Union (2023) *Regulation (EU) 2023/2854 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2023 on the making available on the Union market and the export from the Union of certain commodities and products associated with deforestation and forest degradation*. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/2854/oj/eng>

Eurostat (2024) *Food waste and food waste prevention – estimates, European*. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?%20title=Food_waste_and_food_waste_prevention_-_estimates

FAO (2025a) *Climate Smart Agriculture*. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/climate-smart-agriculture/en/>

FAO (2025b) *Crop production | Climate-Smart Agriculture*. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/climate-smart-agriculture/knowledge/practices/crop-production/en/>

FAO (2016) *Global Standard to Measure Food Loss and Waste: Food Loss and Waste Accounting and Reporting Standard*. FAO. Available at: https://flwprotocol.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/FLW_Standard_final_2016.pdf

FEFAC (2018) *EU Code of Conduct on agricultural data sharing by contractual agreement*. Available at: https://fefac.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/eu_code_of_conduct_on_agricultural_data_sharing-1.pdf

FOODPathS (2025) *FOODPathS – Food as Pathways to Sustainability*. Available at: <https://www.foodpaths.eu/>

FutureFoodS Partnership (2025) *FutureFoodS Partnership*. Available at: <https://www.futurefoodspartnership.eu/>

Interreg Europe (2025) *Wasteless Programme in Hungary*, Interregeurope.eu. Available at: [Wasteless Programme in Hungary](#)

Interreg Europe (2024) *Performance-based Tax Return Boosts Organic Waste Recycling*, Interreg Europe. Available at: <https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/performance-based-tax-return-boosts-organic-waste-recycling>

Joint Research Centre: Institute for Prospective Technological Studies, Gomez y Paloma, S., Balázs, B., Eyden-Wood, T., Blackett, M., Schmutz, U., Kneafsey, M., Venn, L., Santini, F., Bos, E., Trenchard, L., & Sutton, G. (2013) *Short food supply chains and local food systems in the EU: a state of play of their socio-economic characteristics*, (S..Gomez y Paloma, editor, F..Santini, edito) Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2791/88784>

Junta de Andalucía (2025) *CreceA -Junta de Andalucía*. Available at: <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/organismos/agapa/estructura/transparencia/informacion-sectorial/proyectos-europeos/crece-and.html>

Marsden, T., Hebinck, P. and Mathijs, E. (2018) 'Re-building food systems: Embedding assemblages, infrastructures and reflexive governance for food systems

transformations in Europe', *Food Security*, 10, pp. 1301–1309. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-018-0870-8>.

Mesiranta, N., Närvänen, E. and Mattila, M. (2022) 'Framings of food waste: How food system stakeholders are responsabilized in public policy debate', *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 41(2), pp. 144–161. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/07439156211005722>

Michel-Villarreal, R., Vilalta-Perdomo, E. L., Canavari, M., & Hingley, M. (2021) *Resilience and Digitalization in Short Food Supply Chains: A Case Study Approach*, *Sustainability*, 13(11), 5913. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13115913>

Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (2025) *Milan Urban Food Policy Pact*. Available at: <https://www.milanurbanfoodpolicypact.org/>

Ministère de l'Agriculture et de l'Alimentation (2025) *Avec le RÉGAL, les collectivités se mobilisent contre le gaspillage alimentaire*. Available at: <https://agriculture.gouv.fr/avec-le-regal-les-collectivites-se-mobilisent-contre-legaspillage-alimentaire>

Nagy, V. (2025) *Outcomes of mapping the best supporting regulations of short food supply chain*, EU4Advice. Available at : <https://eu4advice.eu/outcomes-of-mapping-the-best-supporting-regulations-of-short-food-supply-chains/>

OECD (2019) *Digital Opportunities for Better Agricultural Policies*. Available at: [Digital Opportunities for Better Agricultural Policies | OECD](#)

OECD (2025) "Beyond food loss and waste reduction targets: Translating reduction ambitions into policy outcomes", *OECD Food, Agriculture and Fisheries Papers*, No. 214, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/59cf6c95-en>.

ParmaCAL (2025) *Centro Agroalimentare Logistico di Parma*. Logistica Solidale. Available at: <https://www.calparma.it/logistica-solidale/iniziativa/>

Pijpers, F. and Drabik, D. (2025). Modeling the impact of three FLW reducing policy pathways at the meso level. Part I of Deliverable D1.3 of ZeroW project.

Samen Tegen Voedselverspilling (2025) *Samen Tegen Voedselverspilling*. Available at: <https://samentegenvoedselverspilling.nl/en/>

SchoolFood4Change (2025) *SchoolFood4Change*. Available at: <https://schoolfood4change.eu/>

Strength2Food (2021) *Strategic guide – Short food supply chains (SFSCs)*. Available at: <https://www.strength2food.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/04/Strategic-Guide-Short-Food-Supply-Chains.pdf>

United Nations (2018) *68% of the world population projected to live in urban areas by 2050, UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs (DESA)*. Available at: <https://www.un.org/uk/desa/68-world-population-projected-live-urban-areas-2050-says-un>

Usca, M. and Tisenkopfs, T. (2023) *The resilience of short food supply chains during the COVID-19 pandemic: a case study of a direct purchasing network*, *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 7:1146446. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2023.1146446>

Voge,J., Newiger-Dous, T., Ehrlich, E., Ermann,U., Ernst,D., Haase,D., Egli, L. (2023) *Food loss and waste in community-supported agriculture in the region of Leipzig, Germany*, *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/14735903.2023.2242181>

Wageningen University & Research (2025) *Akkerweb - WUR*. Available at: <https://www.wur.nl/en/value-creation-cooperation/partnerships-collaborations/wdcc2/data-portal/former-spotlight-datasets/dataset-akkerweb.htm>

Wong, E., Zheng, J., Dhanoa, H., Wang, A., & Li, A. (2021) *Gaming Against Food Waste: Using Gamification to Reduce Consumer Food Waste Behaviour*, Vancouver: University of British Columbia, SEEDS Sustainability Program. Available at: <https://sustain.ubc.ca/sites/default/files/seedslibrary/PSYCH%20421%20Gaming%20Against%20Food%20Waste%20Final%20Report.pdf>

WRI (2016) *Food Loss and Waste Accounting and Reporting Standard*, Food Loss and Waste Protocol, World Resources Institute, Washington, DC. Available at: <https://www.wri.org/research/food-loss-and-waste-accounting-and-reporting-standard>

Zero Waste Week (2025) *Zero Waste Week Reducing Landfill Waste Since 2008*. Available at: <https://www.zerowasteweek.co.uk/>

ZeroW Deliverable 8.2. De Carluccio, A., Guillou, A., Dorigo Salamon, N., Deschepper, M., Pascual, M.A., Turlea, A.L., van der Weerdt, C. (2025). D8.2: 'Just' transition pathway & intermediate targets. *ZeroW project*.

FAO (2025a) *Climate Smart Agriculture*. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/climate-smart-agriculture/en/>

[i] Food Policy Councils (FPCs) are innovative governance tools that support food system transformation. They connect citizens and stakeholders to identify issues, support initiatives, promote sustainable, healthy, and just food systems, and link civil society with government to influence policy. Most FPCs operate locally, though some exist at regional or national levels. For more, see: den Boer et al. (2023).

[ii] For instance, SILL4's analysis of food redistribution in Barcelona revealed that even in cities with progressive policies, fragmented roles and poor coordination can undermine impact. Political responsibility for food waste is often split across departments, with unclear leadership and scattered budgets, a pattern also seen in Belgium. Monitoring governance indicators, such as the presence of formal agreements, transparency of roles, or cross-sector steering bodies, can help illuminate such gaps and support institutional reform.